

ROBUST

CRISIS GOVERNANCE IN TURBULENT TIMES

Comparative Analysis of Multi-Level Governance during Crises: How interactivity influences robust governance.

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1. Introduction

Multilevel governance (MLG) is not only a highly debated notion in the academic literature on public policy, but also a normative idea underlying discussions in various – local, regional, EU – policymaking circles and fora. From this perspective, MLG offers an alternative paradigm to hierarchical policymaking, by substituting command and control with collaboration and coordination across different levels of government and among all concerned public and non-public actors. It is however still unclear to what extent and under which circumstances MLG emerges in times of crisis. Furthermore, it is also an open question whether and to what extent MLG can contribute to achieve robust crisis governance, implying the capacity to alleviate turbulence (through innovative and/or adaptive responses) without compromising core democratic values and norms. Specifically, it is unclear which types of interactivity within MLG can contribute to achieve robust crisis governance. The existing literature on MLG has acknowledged and critically discussed the normative implications of the concept, e.g., in terms of relations between input and output legitimacy (see Piattoni 2010). The underlying assumption in such debate is that MLG, by securing ample representation of all relevant interests and points of view when making authoritative decisions (input legitimacy), will produce policies that are perceived as being more effective (output legitimacy), and to which all affected parties are more likely to comply with. However, the relation is indeed a complex one, and scholars have also brought to the fore the trade-offs in multilevel governance policymaking between problem-solving capacity and democratic accountability (Papadopoulos 2007 and 2010; Maggetti and Trein 2019). Overall, the link between MLG and the robust governance of crises is still largely under-theorised.

This report aims to fill these gaps, elaborating on data collected through interviews and an extensive analysis of policy documents conducted by the partners of the ROBUST project¹ (see section 3). More specifically, the report builds on the mainly theoretical results of D3.1, aiming to transition to more concrete applications in empirical data and crisis evaluation.

The report is structured into two broad parts.

In the first part, we aim to understand whether and how different types of policymaking relations (more horizontal or more vertical) emerged during recent crises in nine European countries and at the EU level. In particular, we are interested in understanding whether any specific decision-making venues emerged during such crises characterised by the involvement of public actors from different governmental levels and nonpublic actors, and to understand more about the characteristics of such venues. We do so by examining three types of governance responses to the covid19 crisis – the management of lockdowns/closures, testing and tracing (henceforth we refer to this first dimension as “pandemic management”), the management of school closures, and the management of the vaccination campaigns. In addition to that, we look at the management of asylum-seekers’ reception in the ‘refugee crisis’ in Europe, and at governance responses to the financial crisis. While conducting this analysis we focus on governance interactions at the national level (i.e. responses concerning the whole countries, excluding more local/regional types of responses), and at the EU level.

In the second part of the report, we aim to address another key question, namely: how and to what extent can interactivity in multilevel governance policymaking arrangements favour more effective and

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more robust policy responses in times of heightened turbulence (for a definition of robustness and turbulence see Turfing et al. 2023)? To answer this question, we look at a range of governance responses in our case-countries that were explicitly selected by members of the consortium as revealing examples of robust responses to the COVID-19, the refugee, and the financial crises (see section 3). While looking at these robust cases we aim to understand whether such responses were characterised by any multilevel policymaking arrangements or venues (and of which type). While our analysis cannot make definitive conclusions about the links between MLG and robustness, it aims to generate some hypotheses on such link, that will be further tested in the ROBUST project in WP6.

2. Theoretical framework: multi-level governance and key concepts used in this report

This first section of the report recalls some key conceptual elements related to our conceptualisation of MLG and interactivity within MLG venues and arrangements (these are elaborated more in depth in the first WP3 report: Caponio et al. 2023).

2.1. Conceptualisations of MLG and interactivity in MLG.

In academic debates, MLG has been used in a variety of different ways (see the first WP3 report of the ROBUST project, Caponio et al. 2023). At a more generic and abstract level, MLG has been defined as *dispersion of authority* (Hooghe and Marks 2001). Hence, *the generic definition of multilevel governance alludes to processes of dispersion of state authority leading to increasing multilevelness and complexity in contemporary political systems*. Such broad conceptualisation of MLG as a synonym for multilevel politics (Scholten 2013) has often been the object of sharp criticism as, following such broad definition, “any complex and multi-faceted political process can be referred to as multilevel governance” (Peters and Pierre 2004, 88).

In parallel, the notion of MLG has also acquired more specific meanings. Following Alcantara and Nells, two different understanding of MLG can be singled out in the literature. The first understanding emerges from studies on systems of government, and more specifically on European integration and federalism. These studies conceptualised MLG as a *system of authority allocation* characterised by increased multilevelness, as reflected by processes of internationalisation/Europeanization and decentralization of national states. Theoretical elaboration and empirical investigations focus primarily on formal structures of division of competence across different types of jurisdictions, building upon Hooghe and Marks' (2003) two types of multilevel governance, i.e.: type I MLG, that describes a governing system based on a limited number of clearly defined non-overlapping territorial jurisdictions, each with a ‘bundle’ of functions, essentially mirroring federalist systems; and type II MLG, defined as a more anarchical order of single-purpose or task-specific jurisdictions with overlapping memberships.

The second understanding instead, relies to research on policy networks and modes of governance and defines multilevel governance as *an instance of policymaking* presenting three key and distinctive features: 1) *different levels of government are simultaneously involved*; 2) *non-governmental actors at different levels are also involved*; 3) *relationships defy existing hierarchies and take the form of non-hierarchical networks*. Whereas the systems approach to MLG focuses on macro-processes and structures, the instance approach characterises as intrinsically relational and meso-level, and it draws attention to the specific features that distinguish MLG interactions vis-à-vis other possible modes of policymaking characterised by different levels of cooperation (or a lack thereof) in the vertical/intergovernmental and in the horizontal/state-society dimensions. Alcantara and Nells (2014) for instance, distinguish MLG from intergovernmental relations (see also: Scholten 2013; Caponio 2022a).

This report adopts this latter perspective, and therefore is specifically interested in interactions among actors within MLG arrangements.

How does interactivity within multilevel governance arrangements take place and which different varieties or configurations can it take? Empirical research carried out in North America and Europe highlights that MLG can assume quite distinct forms. More specifically, US scholars have emphasised the pivotal role of municipal authorities in establishing multi-layered networks (see: Agranoff 2018; Kaufmann and Sidney 2020). They conceptualised MLG as a process of bottom-up mobilisation, where local governments represent key nodes connecting multiple governmental and non-governmental actors. In contrast, MLG arrangements in Europe often take place in the 'shadow of hierarchy' (Börzel 2010), that is depending on the interest and willingness of governmental actors at the EU and, even more, at a national level, to establish and legitimise multilevel networks and venues (see e.g. Curry 2016; Dąbrowski, Bachtler and Bafoil 2014; depending on the policy issue and on the institutional structure, intermediate regional levels can be also critical see e.g. Ravazzi 2018). In Canada the notion of MLG has been used to capture the functioning of concrete processes of policymaking beyond the formal structures of the federalist system (Gagnon 2018), bringing to the fore the complex dynamics of negotiation and collaboration between provinces, cities and, depending on the issue, different categories of non-governmental actors (see e.g. Alcantara and Nelles 2014; Alcantara, Broschek, and Nelles 2016; Papillon 2012; Tamtik and Colorado 2022; Sutcliffe 2012).

Overall, critical scholars look at interactivity within MLG arrangements as highly selective in terms of participants, prevalently informal (and therefore rather obscure) and potentially in conflict with the representative principles underlying democratic institutions. However, their general critique of MLG does not reflect on the different configurations that interactivity can assume within specific MLG arrangements and processes, and that, we posit, can lead to different outcomes in terms of effectiveness and legitimacy of policy responses. In other words, especially in times of crises and to address the ensuing turbulence, different variants of MLG might be more or less able to ensure robust governance as defined by Ansell, Sørensen & Torfing (2023) as the capacity to ensure, at the same time, that efficient solutions are pursued and principles of democratic legitimacy and accountability are fulfilled.

To make sense of such complexity this report explores in depth the issue of interactivity within governance processes, focusing specifically on the decision-making stage of the policy cycle.

2.2. Key features of governance arrangements/venues.

The following classification of governance arrangements and venues is based on the identified governance responses to the three crises from nine European countries. It is essential to underline here that we do not merely focus on MLG processes strictly speaking, i.e. processes taking place on both the horizontal and vertical dimension of policymaking, but also account for processes taking place only on one of these axes, thus either vertical or horizontal alone (despite our primary interest being on MLG processes). The next paragraphs present the characteristics underlying our classification.

At the most basic level, we distinguish between *governance venues* and *governance arrangements*. Venues are physical or digital places where all actors get together for decision making. We distinguish in the report among MLG venues (including public actors from different levels and nonpublic actors), vertical/intergovernmental venues (including public actors from different levels but no nonpublic actor) and horizontal venues (including public actors from one governmental level and nonpublic actors). The concept of arrangement instead refers to governance relations, negotiations and collaborations between actors that do not take place within a venue, but rather through separate interactions between subgroups of actors. An example of MLG arrangement is a situation in which a national government develops separate and occasional consultations, outside of any venue, with nonpublic actors and local governments to gather information useful for decision-making.

We then identify seven key dimensions of horizontal, vertical or multilevel (i.e. horizontal and vertical) governance arrangements and venues. Such dimensions have been identified using a mixed inductive and deductive strategy, i.e. these were partly derived from the existing literature and partly identified inductively from the results of our analyses.

The first dimension refers to *the types of actors involved*. As highlighted above, governance arrangements or venues can have a quite diverse composition in terms of type of participants. We distinguish between merely horizontal arrangements, merely vertical arrangements and then, in the case of multilevel governance arrangements, among primarily intergovernmental arrangement (which engage governmental actors and only few representatives of non-public stakeholders, therefore privileging interactions on the vertical/intergovernmental dimension of policymaking processes) and primarily multi-stakeholder arrangements (which include a broader range of non-governmental actors on the horizontal/state-society dimension). We can expect that the prevalence of either type of actors will influence multilevel governance interactivity, which is likely to be more hierarchical when the vertical dimension prevails, and more cooperative when there is a wide participation of non-public actors.

The second dimension regards the 'who takes the initiative' i.e. the *initial promoters*. Arrangements or venues can be established top-down by EU institutions and/or national governments or bottom-up, as a result of the pressure or formal requests put forward by local governments and/or non-governmental organisations on higher levels of government.

A third important and related dimension is that of *the type of leadership steering the process*. Governance arrangements or venues can be steered by national authorities or rather more bottom-up by lower-level governmental authorities or nonpublic actors. Such steering relates to the overall coordination of the operative work of the governance arrangement and, specifically, to which actors are responsible for deciding e.g., which organizations/institutions take part in the discussions and in which sessions.

The fourth dimension refers to the *level of formality of the interactions* that take place within a governance arrangement or venue. These relations can either be hierarchical (if these are strictly controlled by the higher-level governmental authorities, i.e., if the interactions take the form of a mere consultation of other actors on specific issues) or non-hierarchical, e.g., if actors interact informally and higher-level governments are open to receiving inputs from other actors also on issues that are not part of the formal agenda. In fact, even when participants are primarily governmental authorities, governance arrangements or venues can still be still characterised by a high level of informality, especially at international or EU level, where hierarchical relations are less stringent, as highlighted by the frequent and informal interactions between the European Commission and local authorities on various matters (see e.g., Piattoni 2010; Caponio 2022). At the same time, the participation of a wide range of different non-governmental actors in multilevel governance decision-making venues might require some degree of formalisation of interactions in order to facilitate effective decision-making.

Fifth, and specifically for the case of governance venues, it is possible to distinguish between venues according to their *degree of institutionalisation*. We distinguish between highly formal and institutionalised venues – if they correspond to some kind of institutional bodies or take place in the context of formalised institutional structures – and venues that are more informal and less institutionalised – e.g., that take place through online meetings or in fora that do not correspond to formalised institutional bodies.

Also, in the case of venues, it is interesting to distinguish among venues that *already existed before* the crises, and venues that were created *ad hoc* to deal with the crises at stake.

Finally, for both governance venues and arrangements it is relevant to ask whether these reproduce or emerge in the context of specific *structures* of distributed competences, or whether they defy or aim to move beyond existing structures.

Figure 1 graphically presents the **varieties of multilevel governance venues** that can be identified at the intersection of the first four dimensions (type of actors involved, promoters/leadership and formality of interactions). Regarding levels of formality, this dimension is captured in terms of degrees within each variant of MLG, with light grey indicating formal interactions and dark grey informal interactions.

Table 1. Varieties of MLG venues.

	Primarily intergovernmental	Multi-stakeholders
Top-down	Club	Forum
Bottom-up	Interest-group	Assembly

The *club* variant of multilevel governance reflects arrangements or processes started top-down by governmental authorities that admit only a limited number of stakeholders (NGOs for instance) selected because of the key resources they can provide to the solving of the issues at hand. It functions as a club since participation is on invitation only, and it can take either a more formal or informal style of interactions based on personal relations of trust and acquaintance. However, top-down multilevel governance arrangements can also point at favouring the participation of all relevant stakeholders that can provide precious resources in addressing a specific issue, for instance trade unions, employers' associations, housing agencies, community self-help groups, voluntary associations etc. In this case, we will have a *forum-like* multilevel governance arrangement, which again can be characterised by more or less formalized interactions. The *interest group* and the *assembly* variants instead, are both started bottom-up by the initiative and leadership of local authorities and/or grassroots organisations, but present different degrees of inclusion of stakeholders. In the interest group-like multilevel governance, a restricted group of key stakeholders representing a certain local/regional area get together in order to put pressure on higher levels of government on a specific issue or situation. In the case of the assembly, instead, a broader alliance of local level public and non-public actors convenes initiatives and events like conferences to which representatives of higher-ranked levels of government are involved.

2.3. Three important notes.

Before moving to the analysis, it is important to make three clarifications.

First, while the MLG literature has also often focused on implementation rather than on decision-making, in this report we do specifically focus on this latter phase of the policy cycle. This, on the one hand, is in line with invitations by scholars to explore MLG and governance relations in early stages of the policy cycle (see e.g. Dabrowski, 2014: 357; Geddes and Taylor 2016, 590). On the other hand, this allows us to avoid overlaps with analyses conducted in WP4 of the Robust project, which focus on governance hybridity and network governance specifically, with a focus on dynamics of policy implementation.

Second, while the MLG literature does not provide definitive conclusions as to which specific types of nonpublic actors must be involved in policymaking relations in order for such relations to be qualified as 'horizontal governance relations'. In this specific report, we only refer to nonpublic actors as nonpublic *organizations*. We therefore exclude from our analysis individual *experts* that were involved in governance processes in the crises. This is, on the one hand, due to the fact that these experts are

involved in decision-making processes because of their specific knowledge/expertise, and not as representatives of any kind of broader organizations/institutions. On the other hand, this allows us to avoid any overlaps with WP5 of the Robust project on “societal intelligence” which looks specifically at patterns of interactions (and knowledge interfaces) among policymakers and experts.

Third, in this report we only look at vertical interactions that involved national governments and lower levels of government (regional, provincial, local). MLG interactions that involve higher levels of government (e.g., supranational institutions) fall outside of the scope of this report.

3. Methodology

This deliverable relies on insights from empirical evidence on governance relations across the three above-mentioned crises in nine European countries (Belgium, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Hungary, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway and Spain). This was complemented by secondary data drawn from public administration, crisis, and knowledge management literature.

The primary emphasis for the data collection has been on the COVID-19 pandemic, which represented a similar existential threat to all of the nine countries. Furthermore, the recency of the COVID-19 pandemic provided opportunities for primary data collection with stakeholders reflecting on their recent experiences. This enables deeper insight towards cross-organisational dynamics, which is more difficult to capture with the refugee but especially with the financial crisis, with limitations regarding institutional memory amongst both practitioners and scholars.

The data collection process was coordinated by the leaders of the three empirical WPs of the ROBUST project (WP3-5) and the project coordinators, through a joint 22-page data gathering template, which was developed in collaboration with all the partners to incorporate the flexibility for the idiosyncrasies of the different administrative contexts. The development of the template built on the conceptualisation of both dependent and independent variables of the ROBUST project outlined in D2.1, D3.1, D4.1 and D5.1. The template consisted of three core parts across the three crises under study:

1. Information on the crisis and response (pre-crisis preparedness, turbulence during crisis, crisis responses);
2. Information on the dependent variable (innovativeness and adaptiveness);
3. Information on the independent variables (MLG, hybridity, societal intelligence).

Within the COVID-19 pandemic, the data collection template included a national level analysis as well as two mini-cases connected with the policy measures that were common amongst the countries experiencing the Covid-19 pandemic, i.e. measures related to *school closures*, and the organization of the *vaccination campaign*. Both areas highlight prominent policy measures that were implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic and reflected the ability of governments to adjust to meet the new challenges (Boin et al., 2021). Some partners worked on a third minicase related to the covid-19 pandemic, and on two minicases concerning, respectively, the refugee crisis and the financial crisis.

Additional data were gathered on governance processes at the EU level, mainly through analysis of secondary sources. For this report we also relied on in-depth interviews on MLG during the refugee crisis conducted in the framework of the MinMUS project (see Caponio 2022).

Altogether 108 interviews were conducted in the Consortium. Interviewees included representatives of national, regional and local public sector decisionmakers; public health agency manager; politicians/administrators in central government; civil society organization staff; experts and task force members; journalists having covered the relevant mini-case. Recruitment of interviewees was done with gender balance in mind. This provided a more comprehensive picture of the empirical examples, which enabled to better understand the linkages between the relevant factors. The mini-cases chosen varied

from local to regional to national level, which enabled to better comprehend the factors relevant at different governmental levels. Such rich data allowed to explore and further theorize on the linkages between MLG and robustness, as presented in this deliverable. These linkages will be further studied in WP6, which conducts an in-depth empirical analysis.

PART 1: MLG AND CRISES

4. The role of MLG in responses to the covid-19 pandemic crisis, the refugee crisis and the financial crisis.

This section aims to identify governance relations that emerged in response to the covid-crisis in the nine countries analysed in the decision-making stage of the policy cycle. Insights provided in these sections are derived from the more extensive country reports written by researchers of the ROBUST consortium in each of the nine countries. In particular, we aim to assess whether any kind of (horizontal and/or vertical) policymaking relations emerged in these countries, and, if so, which kind of governance arrangements and venues emerged (examining the dimensions identified in the previous section). We specifically focus on national responses, and do not cover in this section local or regional responses (i.e. responses that emerged in specific areas of the countries analysed, regardless of the governmental levels responsible for such actions).

4.1. The covid-19 pandemic crisis.

While analysing responses to the covid-19 pandemic crisis at the national level we distinguish between three types of responses: first, responses related to the overall pandemic management (i.e. key decisions related to the establishment of nation-wide lockdowns, the closure and/or re-opening of commercial activities and social distancing rules, and the definition of strategies of testing and/or tracing); second, responses related specifically to school closures and reopening; third, responses related to the organization of the vaccination campaign and promotion.

Pandemic management (lockdowns, strategies on testing and tracing)

Table 2 provides an overview of governance relations emerged in the framework of the overall pandemic management (as defined above). As the table suggests, these responses to the crisis were characterised by a prevalence of centralised modes of governance and a limited emergence of vertical relations. We examine responses developed in each of the eight EU countries briefly here below.

Table 2. Overview of governance relations related to pandemic management (lockdowns, testing and tracing etc.).

	Type of governance relations	Venue or arrangement	Type of actors involved	Promoters / initiators	Formality of relations	Leadership / Steering of the venue	Formal/ institutionalised venue or informal venue	Pre-existing bodies/ venues or new ones?	Overall structure of distributed competences?
Belgium	Vertical relations	Venues	NG and RGs	Top-down	Hierarchical	Top-down	Institutionalised venues	Pre-existing	Yes
Czechia	High centralisation								Centralisation partly defies existing structures
Denmark	Centralisation (with limited vertical consultations)								Centralisation aligns with clear structure of distributed competencies
Estonia	Vertical Relations	Arrangement	NG; LGs; regional bodies	Top-down	Hierarchical				No
Hungary	MLG	Venue (but rarely both dimensions present at the same time)	Dominated by NG; selected participation of nonpublic actors and LGs.	Top-down	Non-hierarchical	Top-down	institutionalised venue	New	Top-down venue partly defies existing structures
Italy	Vertical relations	Venue	NG and RGs	NG	Hierarchical	Top-down	Institutionalised venue	Pre-existing	Yes
Netherlands	MLG	Arrangement	LGs, safety regions, various nonpublic actors	Top-down	Hierarchical				Yes
Spain	Vertical relations	Venue	NG and RGs	Top-down	unclear	Top-down	Institutionalised	New	Yes

Belgium. Competencies over health policies in Belgium are scattered amongst the three levels of government, thus requiring some form of vertical coordination, which in non-crisis times takes place through the Inter-ministerial Conference on Public Health. To respond to the covid-19 crisis, however, a separate multilevel emergency response structure was created, which partially reflected the internal organization of the Belgium federal state with some the adaptations. At the outset of the crisis, in March 2020, decision-making processes were highly centralised and top-down, with the federal government making key decisions, with the support of information, data and expertise from lower levels of government. The widespread impact of the pandemic on policy areas of competence of regional and community governments soon required the involvement in crisis management of all levels of government. Hence, membership of the most important crisis management body, the NSC, a federal body consisting of the Prime Minister and the Deputy Prime Ministers, was extended to include the Ministers-President of the Regions and Communities. The Risk Management Group (RMG), a federal focal point responsible for liaising with the EU and the WHO, also comprised representatives of the health authorities from the federal state and the federated entities. In mid-2020, a federal decree granted powers to the regional and municipal authorities to deal and manage the crisis, but when the number of infections raised again in late 2020, the federal government took again the lead. In October 2020, the Corona Commissariat was created to coordinate the national response to the pandemic. This was a unit headed by the so-called “Corona Commissioner” and backed by the Prime Minister’s Office and the Health Minister’s Office. The Commissariat served as single coordinator for the crisis response and streamlined the coordination processes across various government levels, including local authorities. Additionally, the government transferred the primary decision-making authority from the NSC to the Concertation Committee, composed of the federal prime minister and 23 ministers the federal and federated executives. Amongst the various ad hoc multilevel platforms, an inter-federal Testing Task Force was established within the Corona Commissariat in October 2020 and a permanent Testing Working Group to help define and operationalize the testing policy. Under the leadership of the expert Prof. Herman Goossens, the Testing Task Force was established by the Inter-ministerial Conference on Public Health and consisted of experts, field specialists and representatives from all federal and federated administrations, making it a consultative body whose goal was to achieve a coherent, integrated and flexible testing policy for the population. Overall, decision-making processes related to the pandemic management in Belgium were therefore characterised by primarily vertical relations among the national government and subnational governments. These relations were formalised in different intergovernmental bodies/venues. Relations were initiated top-down by the national level, in the context of the highly formalised multilevel institutional structure of the Belgian state, and were mostly hierarchical.

Czechia. Conversely, pandemic management in Czechia was highly centralised. The national response to COVID-19 was mainly top-down led by the Government and the Prime minister Babiš (who did not have any formal responsibility in this sense according to the pandemic plan in place at the time), and the Ministry of Health (including the Chief Public Health Officer who was a Deputy Minister of Health). The main pandemic management body was the Integrated Central Management Team, headed by the Chief Public Health Officer. Permanent members included two representatives of the Ministry of Healthcare and two representatives of the army. The role of the Central Epidemiologic Commission was somehow put aside, it met only several times and its meetings were interrupted in May 2020 for four months which was criticized by media, because the pandemic plan expected that the commission would meet regularly and exchange information with central authorities and regions in all phases of a pandemic. When lockdowns and closures of different types of activities were decided, sub-national governments had to comply with national measures and did not have any discretion (with very limited exceptions e.g., in relation to children wellbeing). Some of the interviews conducted for the ROBUST project suggest that in the first wave decision-making processes were not only highly centralised but also ‘army-like’. As the time flew, the decision making of central bodies became more participatory, i.e., representatives of different types of institutions were invited to the meetings on a temporary basis. Such temporary members included the head of the unit for public health protection of the Ministry of Healthcare, permanent members of the ÚKŠ, other representatives of Ministry of Healthcare, Ministry of Defence, Ministry of the Interior, army, and representatives of police, fire brigade, or association of general practitioners. In one interview the involvement of a wider number of organizations in the

meetings was attributed to 'pressure from presidents of regions, mayors and regional vaccination coordinators'.

Estonia. Also in Estonia, pandemic management was characterised by the emergence of vertical relations among the national government and subnational governments. The Health Board and other public health organizations were forced to quickly adopt, tighten cooperation, and reorganize some work to focus on solving the crisis. The Health Board particularly intensified collaboration with local governments, which were reliant on the advice and data shared by the board to take proportional measures to lessen the spread of the virus and had an interest in being involved in key decisions that directly affected them. Regular meetings were therefore held between regional coordinators of the Health Board, regional crisis commissions of the Rescue Board and municipalities. Therefore, vertical relations were largely non-formalised, initiated top-down by the national level and mostly hierarchical.

Denmark. Emergency plans in Denmark stipulated a clear chain of command from the Public Health Authority (under the Ministry of Health) over the regions to the municipalities. No plan existed for involving municipalities, schools, private workplaces and other actors in decisions related to curbing the spread of the virus. Thus, cooperation on pandemic control had between the public health authorities and all these other actors had to be developed very rapidly. Such cooperation was highly successful, probably because of existing modes of cooperation between the state, region and municipalities within other areas. In particular, two coordination units with the central government were very important for decision-making and strategic coordination between the ministries and their interventions. Firstly, the permanent coordination unit, made up by the ministers and department heads of state, treasury, foreign affairs, tax and justice. A second coordination unit was established to deal exclusively with the pandemic made up by the ministers of: health, justice, treasury, foreign affairs and culture. This unit was key in formulating and coordinating day-to-day interventions regarding closures, testing and vaccination. Overall, decision-making processes related to the pandemic management in Denmark were therefore characterised by high centralisation. Subnational governments were not represented in key decision-making bodies but were consulted during the pandemic and played a key role in implementation. Consultations were initiated top-down by the national level, in the context of the formalised multilevel institutional structure of the Danish state, and were mostly hierarchical.

Hungary. Management of the pandemic in Hungary was overall highly centralised (Hajnal et al., 2021, p. 618) and governance responses to the pandemic in Hungary also led to a restructuring of the vertical dimension of multi-level government and, specifically, several restrictions to the funding, autonomy and policy-making capacity of (particularly opposition-led) local governments, and a parallel transfer of tasks to local governments, e.g. tasks related to prevention and containment measures such as the organization of social services to them. This placed local governments under a "dual pressure stemming from their coordinating role in the organisation of local anti-epidemic efforts, and sharply declining revenues under the principle of burden-sharing" (Kovács, 2020, p. 217). Within and despite such centralised institutional framework, pandemic management in Hungary was characterised by a quite peculiar MLG venue, which had very limited consultative functions. In the country, the central institutional locus of the pandemic governance was a new type of organizational arrangement, the Coronavirus Operative Staff. The group was led by the Minister of Interior in his role as Deputy Prime Minister, and additional members included the Minister of Human Capacities (as co-leader of the group), the Chief Medical Officer, leaders of the police, the National Ambulance Service, the National Directorate General for Disaster Management, and a few other officials (Csehi, 2023). The prime minister had the capacity to join and head any meetings of the OS. Albeit being a (formally) non-hierarchical, collegial body, the OS included individuals from very different levels of the administrative hierarchy. Moreover, the membership included highly visible politicians as well as ones in strictly technical/professional roles. The group was open and flexible; additional ad hoc participants from whatever types of organizations – including heads of any central or local government bodies – could be invited to discuss topics of key importance, as it was deemed necessary by the group's leader, in both the main group and the subcommittees. Unfortunately, very little is known about how the OS operated as the structure and frequency of occasional invitees are strictly classified. Anecdotal evidence suggests that local governments and some nonpublic actors (e.g., the Chamber of Agriculture and the Chamber of

Commerce) were sometimes involved in the meetings. The frequency of meetings was left for the members of the leaders to decide on a case-by-case basis. The working of the Staff was highly secretive. Participants were (and continue to be) not allowed to talk about in inner workings of the Staff, and news media were generally not allowed to ask questions (or only in extremely selective and limited ways). The formal authority of the OS was mostly related to the formulation and review of public policies in connection with the pandemic, as well as the coordination of their implementation. The issues to be dealt with, and the role (i.e. identifying/understanding problems, suggesting solutions, or making decisions) to be played by the Staff, similarly to membership, are decided by the executive leader (in the case of the Operative Staff, the Prime Minister). Whether and to what extent in what ways the specifically “operative staff” features were triggered and utilized in decision-making was subject to a high-level decision. In the case of the OS, this typically meant the decision of the Prime Minister, whereas in the case of OS subcommittees it was up to the subcommittee leader at hand. Similarly, deciding on the permanent or ad hoc inclusion or exclusion of staff members was subject to executive decision. Politically significant decisions usually bypassed the OS and were made at the Cabinet level. Local governments had then to implement decisions taken at the national level. Interviewees suggest that the OS was characterised by smooth and effective cooperation, in particular at the OS subcommittee level, where most decisions were taken by consensus. Therefore, the Operative Staff as the main crisis governance body and its associated background committees were a rather limited case of ideal-typical centralized MLG, as they were established (and potentially presided over) by the prime minister and had formalized, hierarchical relations. The consultative arrangement behind the OS involved some participation of organizations outside the public administration (including from service and academic organizations) and a very limited participation of local governments. However, membership in this venue was decided in a strictly top-down and highly subjective manner (for example, during the first wave local governments were not included in the Operative Staff despite their key role; so was the case with NGO representatives). The range of members was strongly filtered: businesses, local governments or their associations, the NGO sector, any actor tied to political parties, and international or EU-level entities were excluded.

Italy. In the initial phase of the pandemic the Italian government was determined to maintain total central control over all decisions pertaining to regions (Capano 2020). The Prime Minister stated that it would end in chaos if all the regions went their separate ways. The government thus made it a requirement that any local authorities referred to the Department of Civil Protection before issuing any regulatory ordinances. As a result, the Italian government response to covid-19 was characterized by a high conflict, ongoing disputes over management of the pandemic and poor levels of coordination between the central government and different regional levels (Bull 2021; Giovannini and Mosca 2021). During the pandemic's second wave, however, the national government developed structural consultations and negotiations with the regions. Such negotiations took place in the context of a highly formalised venue – the so-called ‘Conferenza permanente per i rapporti tra lo Stato, le Regioni e le Province autonome’ (Permanent Conference for the Relations between the State, the Regions and the Autonomous Provinces) – which pre-existed the covid-19 pandemic, involving governmental actors at the national and regional level, and experts (but, remarkably, neither private actors nor civil society actors, nor local governments).

The Netherlands. In the Netherlands, pandemic management was characterised by a loose MLG arrangement, not formalised in any venue. Overall, during the COVID-19 Crisis, a clear top-down structure was put in place: decisions were made at the national level and implemented at the regional and local levels. The national government provided frameworks within which regional and local authorities could operate. This allowed for some variation between regions, although not substantial, ensuring a degree of flexibility. For example, regional emergency regulations could be adopted by 25 collectives of municipalities (‘safety regions’). This resulted in different levels of strictness of the measures in the safety regions. However, some vertical and horizontal relations developed in the framework of this highly centralized framework. In late January 2020, a governance coordination board (LOT-C) was started under the leadership of the Minister of Health, Welfare, and Sport – which qualifies as a vertical policymaking venue – involving Dutch Safety Regions, the Association of Dutch Municipalities, the Municipal Health Services (GGD), and healthcare consortia. These meetings focused on the administrative aspects of a potentially imminent infectious disease crisis and later on its

evaluation. The recommendations of the Outbreak Management Team (OMT), consisting of experts in epidemiology, were initially presented to this forum to assess their administrative feasibility and desirability. LOT-C was tasked with conveying information to the national government regarding issues faced by safety regions, as well as compliance status and required capacity. Furthermore, there was extensive consultation between the national government, unions, employer organizations, public transportation entities, the education sector, and the health sector regarding the easing of measures. While the national crisis structure activated in early March 2020 demonstrated a formalized institutionalized approach, later on the involvement of various actors at different levels was a key feature. Initially, the national government collaborated with expert teams and safety regions. Later, a wide range of stakeholders, including municipalities, healthcare professionals, stakeholder organizations, actively participated in the crisis response. This demonstrated a broader engagement beyond the vertical/intergovernmental dimension. At the onset of the pandemic, a National Consortium for Medical Supplies was also established, mostly with implementation functions but that also provided a venue for decision-making processes on primary responses to the pandemic. This initiative, initiated by the ministry, involved professionals from hospitals, academic centres, suppliers, and manufacturers aimed at collectively procuring essential medical equipment without profit interests. Private companies and experts were also invited by the national government and GGD to contribute ideas on the use of technology during the pandemic. In conclusion, in the absence of specific MLG venues where all actors gathered simultaneously there was a kind of loose MLG arrangement in place characterised by separate horizontal and vertical interactions strictly coordinated by the national government. This “arrangement” established to support decision-making processes, especially during the initial phases of the crisis, was highly top-down, intergovernmental and characterised by a high degree of informality. The national government, particularly the Ministry of Health, Welfare, and Sport, played a central role in directing the response.

Spain. Pandemic management in Spain was characterised by quite visible vertical policymaking relations. The first months of the crisis, in fact, were characterised by highly centralised responses (e.g. Navarro and Velasco, 2022). At the beginning of May 2020, a co-governance plan was established which set a certain level of decentralization to involve regional governments in the management of the crisis. This co-governance process allowed regional governments to make proposals about general measures to be taken for the whole country and of specific measures in their regions. In this phase, proposed measures and initiatives were analysed by the correspondent regional government and the Ministry of Health. The idea was to get an agreement between both governmental levels, though the final decision corresponded to the central government. While the ‘state of emergency’ lasted until the 21st of June 2020 at that point the de-escalation plan in order to return to a “new normality” approved the 28th of April 2020 entered into force, with the above-mentioned framework of co-governance. Navarro and Velasco (2022) argue that this (new) approach was the result of the “absence of effective vertical coordination schemes that could have worked as an alternative”. The process of “devolution” from the central government to regional governments resulted in the need of cooperation between these two governmental levels. A legal reform, approved by almost all parties in the Parliament reinforced the mechanisms for vertical coordination on health issues via some changes in the functioning of the Inter-territorial Council of the National Health System. Due to the increase of cases after the 2020 summer, a second “state of alarm” was declared from the 25th of October 2020, initially approved until the 9th of November 2020, but was progressively extended until the 9th May 2021. This second state of alarm maintained the decentralization approach previously approved. It is worth highlighting that the Constitutional Court, the main supreme court in Spain, declared illegal different aspects of both the first and second states of alarm.

School closures

Governance relations related to school closures identified in our 8 countries are illustrated in table 3 below. Overall, compared to the overall pandemic management, such responses were characterised by a higher involvement of nonpublic actors, along the horizontal dimension of MLG.

Belgium. Decisions on school closures in Belgium were mainly made by the Ministries of Education of the three communities, which has close contacts with a variety of actors. All the regional Ministers of Education had regular meetings with a quite broad consultation group including diverse education stakeholders, such as parents' representatives, teachers, trade unions, psychologists, virologists, and pedagogy experts from the different school networks. Participants were invited to either share directly their expertise (e.g. pedagogy) or to represent their group/organization (e.g. trade unions). In the case of the Flemish region, this group also directly included student representatives. These consultation rounds were held at the invitation of the regional Minister and organized ad-hoc for the crisis. However, some of the actors involved were already part of more institutionalized and pre-existing bodies, such as the VLOR (the strategic advisory board for education in Flanders). This body was still active during the pandemic, keeping its customary task of providing advice. However, it was not exploited as an existing venue nor entrusted with additional tasks. The interviews conducted by the ROBUST project also suggest that such collaboration during the crisis fostered consensus among the nonpublic actors involved. As an illustration, networks of schools that were not used to working together before the crisis aimed at presenting a united front during these meetings.

Czechia. Key decisions on school closures in Czechia were made by central bodies, especially the Ministry of Healthcare. Municipalities and regions, nor private schools, could not make autonomous decisions on school closures and had to comply with national measures (with very limited exceptions). Interestingly such highly centralized management was partially at odd with the overall institutional structure of the education sector in the Czech Republic. Most of the preschools and primary schools are public and formally under the responsibility of the municipalities according to the law. Public primary schools are usually autonomous legal entities funded from two main sources (municipalities and the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports).

Denmark. In Denmark, public schools are financed and organized by the municipalities. Thus, within the legal framework set by the Ministry of Children and Education, everything from hiring and firing of teachers, budgeting, planning of physical locations of school, partial decision on school syllabus, and dialogue with parents is governed by the municipalities. However, during the covid-19 pandemic, governance responses were highly centralised. To protect public health while still ensuring some level of education for children, the government employed a mix of outright school closures and partial reopenings. Decisions on closures and (partial or full) reopenings of schools were exclusively taken at central government level during the entire pandemic. Based on advice from the State Serum Institute and the National Health Authority, the government's coordination committee was the key decisionmaker. It seems that the Ministry of Children and Education had a very limited say on these decisions. Instead, the key inspiration on how to deal with the school seems to have come from the European Centre for Disease Control (ECDC) (Grønnegaard Christensen et al., 2021, p. 221). The Ministry disseminated advice to the municipalities on how conduct online and outdoor teaching. The municipalities' interest organization, KL, played a role not in deciding on closures, openings and restrictions, but rather in the calculation and negotiations with the government (the Ministry of Finance) over the financial compensation of municipalities in order to allow them to organize and implement extraordinary teaching practices (Grønnegaard Christensen et al., 2021, pp. 86, 242).

Estonia. In Estonia, different levels and types of organisations worked together to decide and coordinate school closures, as part of an overall MLG arrangement. After the initial wave of state-wide school closures, the Estonian Government opted for a strategy to keep schools open as long as the spread of the virus allowed. The Health Board became an important partner and source of information of schools and municipalities, advising schools on how to contrast the infections and whether a closure should be considered, based on surveillance data. In the second phase of the pandemic, decisions around school closures were left to the discretion of municipalities. As mandated by law, local governments had to consult the national Health Board on school-related decisions. Cooperation between municipalities, schools and the Health Board was tight, as the board provided schools with expert advice and up-to-date epidemiological data, helping guide schools toward proportionate decision-making. The Health Board coordinated this interaction through its regional departments. Regional departments allowed for the coordination of the crisis response on a local level, directly communicating with the municipalities

located in the representative regions. This collaboration (which was entirely new in the Estonian context) enabled municipalities to make flexible, data-based decisions around school lockdowns. Representatives of the regional departments of the Health Board also met with the local governments in regional crisis commissions created by the regional units of the national Estonian Rescue Board (there is no regional government in Estonia). To help combat the multi-tiered crisis in the educational system, the state worked closely together with different non-governmental organisations. Such relations mostly concerned the implementation of specific measures, but these organizations seem also to have provide relevant input for decision-making. For example, together with the Estonian Association of School Psychologists, the Ministry of Education and Research and Estonian Education and Youth board opened a mental health hotline for teachers. The ministry stayed in close contact with different associations of education support specialists (such therapists, psychologists, counsellors) to gather their feedback and think of ways to support the educational system during distance learning. The Ministry of Education and Research also received feedback from NGOs (which were directly involved in the purchase of computers for children) about the problems around organising distance learning as well as concerns about the lack of digital literacy among teachers. Such relations were highly informal, mainly taking place via video calls or phone calls. The Minister of Education and Research also held weekly meetings with Estonian Association of Heads of Schools.

Hungary. Hungary was characterised by an extensive centralisation of public education in the early 2010s, with the central-level government dominating decisions regarding both the organisation, the content, and the methodological focus of public education in Hungary. During the COVID period it was even more like a one-directional avenue of central regulations and highly school-specific decisions (for example, on individual closure) managed and made by the national government. At the central level, the key decision-making actor responsible for defining responses on school closures was the Operative Staff (see above). Within the State Secretariat in charge of public education, the Corona Virus Action Group on Schooling was set up early in the crisis, led by the State Secretary in charge, and staffed by large school operators (the government agency in charge, Klebersberg Center, and major churches) as well as executives of governmental background institutions active in the field of schooling. This Action Group reported to the Operative Staff and the Prime Minister on a weekly basis. The key decisions nevertheless bypassed these forums and were made at the Cabinet level. In matters of less strategic importance, some sectoral network-based solutions emerged. The previously operational sectoral consultation fora (for example, the National Public Education Council, and the Public Education Roundtable) have continued to work during the pandemic period – with the only difference being that they also switched to online communication channels. The State Secretariat in charge of public education has also consulted with the National Student Council online on a monthly basis. A national policymaker interviewed reported that sometimes the Student Council had very good proposals and proposals were sometimes taken on board. The group on schooling, overall, was reported to have “strived to collect information from as many stakeholders as possible”.

Italy. In the first phase of the crisis school closures in Italy were highly centralised, but regional and local governments were given the possibility to implement more restrictions compared to those established by the national government. In the second phase of the crisis the national government provided guidelines that defined some broad principles, leaving to the regions the responsibility to decide how to achieve the goals established, and giving regional governments the competence to decide whether under specific infection rates schools in the region should be closed or not. Definition of such guidelines was the result of consultations between regional governments and the national government in the framework of the above-mentioned State-Regions Conference, a highly institutionalised intergovernmental venue. Overall, these patterns are very much in line with the broader institutional structure of the education sector in Italy. In the education policy field, the State and the Regions have indeed exclusive legislative competences in some sectors, while in other sectors they share responsibilities. Different types of actors, including both governmental and non-governmental actors, across different levels of governance, were later involved in decisions related to the reopening of schools in late 2020. As an official from the Ministry of Education interviewed reported, ‘at the beginning we felt like driving with headlights off, in the dark, conflicting directions, total uncertainty, we couldn’t find a direction and therefore we tried to interact with a number of actors’. The two key

actors involved in the initiative were the Ministry of Education and the Office of the Extraordinary Commissioner for the Covid Emergency. Local governments and trade unions were also involved in the discussions in the summer 2020 that led to the partial school reopening in autumn 2020.

The Netherlands. On the national level, decisions were made hierarchically and in a top-down manner. There was interaction between levels of government in a vertical top-down way, from the minister and the ministry of Health down to municipalities, but such relations mostly concerned policy implementation as, at the municipal level, the stakeholders were responsible for implementing the rules established by the national level. Overall, there were no arenas or tables in which local actors could share their local perspective on the matter, so they were not involved in decision making processes. There was the feeling of an ivory tower in which rules were made that needed to be made workable by the professional on the ground by changing the rules or sometimes even ignoring the rules. As in executing nationally developed policies, local authorities exercised some discretion within the guidelines provided by the ministry, ad hoc collaborative efforts instead emerged among different actors at a local level, but these are outside the scope of this section of the report.

Spain. In Spain, the governance of school closures was characterised by the emergence of both vertical and horizontal relations. The Ministry of Education of the Central Government created a crisis committee made up of politicians and, especially, technicians, who had very frequent meetings with the regional governments (CCAAs) which decided on the general measures for the management of the crisis in the schools. Meetings of this committee were regular and frequent and the way they were organized allowed actors to exchange views and experiences. Most of participants were high-level civil servants from the Ministry of Education and the ministries of the CCAA in charge of educational planning, but also included representatives of nonpublic actors, such as organizations of educators and psychologists, workers, teachers, parents, companies, students. Overall, although CCAAs had autonomy for the implementation of the general guidelines in their own regions, they learned from each other, which also reduced differences in the policies developed in different regions. The Ministries of Health and Education and regional governments specifically met to develop guidelines for the 2020/21 academic year which were used by the regional governments to develop their own protocols for educational centers. Furthermore, the Inter-territorial Council of the National Health Service and the Education Sector Conference, in which the regional governments participate, developed the Prevention, hygiene and health promotion measures against Covid-19 for educational centers in the 2020/21 academic year.

Table 3. Governance relations related to school closures.

	Type of governance relations	Venue or arrangement	Type of actors involved	Promoters / initiators	Formality of relations	Leadership / Steering of the venue	Institutionalised venue or informal venue	Pre-existing or new venues?	In line with overall structure of distributed competences?
Belgium	Horizontal relations	Venue	RGs, trade unions, professional associations, student organizations	Top-down	Non-hierarchical	Top-down	Institutionalised venue	New	Yes (building on previous experiences of horizontal cooperation)
Czechia	High centralisation								Centralisation partly defies existing structures
Denmark	Centralisation								Centralisation not aligned with structure of distributed competencies
Estonia	MLG	Horizontal arrangement + vertical venue	NG, LGs and regional bodies; several; NG and nonpublic actors	Top-down	Hierarchical	(vertical venue: top-down)	(vertical venue: institutionalised)	(vertical venue: new)	Yes
Hungary	Horizontal relations	Sparce venues	NG with various nonpublic actors	Top-down	Non-hierarchical (OS)	Top-down	institutionalised venue	Pre-existing and new (OS)	Yes, aligned with centralised structure of education sector
Italy	MLG	Horizontal arrangement + vertical venue	NG and RGs; NG and nonpublic actors	Top-down	Hierarchical	(vertical venue: top-down)	(vertical venue: institutionalised)	(vertical venue: pre-existing)	Yes
Netherlands	High centralisation								Yes
Spain	MLG	Venue	NG, RGs, wide range of nonpublic actors	Unclear	Non-hierarchical	Unclear	Institutionalised	New	Yes

Vaccination campaigns

Belgium. Promoting and providing vaccinations in Belgium was a responsibility of the three communities. Main actors of reference included the Health Department of the Flemish region, the *Agence pour une Vie de Qualite* of the Wallonia region, and the *Sante section of the Sante section* of the Bruxelles-Capitale region. Federated entities were thus responsible for e.g. the vaccination strategy, the vaccination promotion through campaigns, and the vaccination calendar. While the federal government and the federated entities had exchanges related to the vaccination campaigns, no venue seems to have been created to coordinate such efforts.

Czechia. Despite the high centralisation in the governance of other responses to the covid-19 pandemic, governance of the vaccination in the Czech Republic was characterised by the emergence of both horizontal and vertical relations, which were formalised in MLG venues or arrangements, taking place at the regional level. Regional governments in Czechia were indeed responsible for their vaccination strategies: they had to follow goals included in the strategy decided by the national government, but could decide on how to meet such goals and had some discretion in this respect. The national strategy identified key actors at the strategic level (namely the Ministry of Healthcare, National Vaccination Coordinator, Central Crisis Committee, suppliers of vaccines), at the coordination level (presidents of regions and the mayor of the capital of Prague, National Vaccination Dispatch, regional vaccination coordinators, regional coordinators of general practitioners, distributors of vaccines) and at the implementation level (all types of vaccination places, offices of general practitioners, other providers of medical services if participating in vaccination). The strategy also expected that a humanitarian organization Czech Red Cross will help vaccination teams with administration and that the army might provide vaccination teams with administrative, organizational and technical support. The strategy also explicitly emphasized the role of cooperation for accomplishing of the vaccination strategy among ministries (Ministry of Defence, Ministry of the Interior, Ministry of Labour and Social Services, Ministry of Education) and regional vaccination coordinators and also with other organizations, including companies, employers' associations, professional associations and associations of patients. Each individual region appointed a regional coordinator and coordinated the implementation of the national strategy developing specific regional policies, developing collaborations with local governments and non-public actors. The first vaccination strategy expected that regions would co-decide with the Ministry of Healthcare and municipalities on the network of vaccination centres and the number of vaccines that would be distributed to and within their territories. The interviews suggest that also regional vaccination coordinators were included in the discussion. The national government intervened in the case of establishment of one of the large-scale vaccination centres in Prague (in Prague O2 Universum Arena).

Denmark. In Denmark competences on the vaccination campaign were assigned to the regional level. All five regions established a pandemic commission led by a police chief and staffed with regional politicians, medical and health experts. The regional pandemic commissions were key coordinators of deploying the net of vaccination facilities in dialogue with the municipalities. The new pandemic law adopted in spring 2021 entailed that the regional pandemic commissions were closed and replaced with a single national pandemic commission because the Ministry of Health found that it was necessary to improve coordination of the pandemic efforts between the five regions (Tranberg, 2021). The pandemic commission was truly a MLG forum in the sense that it involved public actors from state, regions and municipalities. It included also private actors as all general practitioners and many specialized doctors from private hospitals.

Estonia. Different types of actors took part in the decision-making process related to the organization of the vaccination campaign in Estonia thanks to the creation of vaccination working groups. These groups included representatives of governmental organizations (Ministry of Social Affairs, Health Board, Estonian Health Insurance Fund, Agency of Medicines, Health and Welfare Information Systems Centre), and other actors such as the Union of General Practitioners, to enable their input and faster communication between the state and private-owned medical centres. Subnational governments however were not involved in this venue. Creating an official format for collaboration between all relevant stakeholders enabled tight coordination and provided a joint platform, where different actors could contribute with their expertise as well as voice potential concerns. The representative actors also

acted as information coordinators within their own organisation by sharing the most recent decisions and changes within the vaccination campaign as well as delegating necessary tasks to their colleagues. As emphasised by multiple stakeholders, the working group format helped bring organisations together, generate new ideas for improving vaccination and streamline the chain of command. The Ministry of Social Affairs also made efforts to communicate with the private sector. For example, meetings were held with labour unions, as well as several networks of employers, such as the Estonian Chamber of Commerce and Industry, Estonian Association of SMEs, and active entrepreneurs. Privately managed health care providers were included through contracting of services by Health Insurance Fund. Some vertical relations also developed between central and local governments. Cooperation between municipalities and the state was facilitated through the Estonian Rescue Board, responsible for the regional crisis governance coordination, and took place through virtual and in-face meetings. This largely concerned policy implementation, but it is likely that some exchanges also took place that influenced national decisions.

Hungary. The Hungarian vaccination policy was characterised by a strictly hierarchical, bureaucratic coordination of planning and logistics: all these elements were exclusively overseen by the County Government Offices at the territorial level, and the Prime Minister's Office overseeing them, at the national level. Local governments, NGOs or private actors played no role in either the planning or the actual dissemination and administering of vaccines. The only important element carrying MLG-like qualities in Hungary's responses related to vaccines was the consultative arrangement present in the Operative Staff and its subcommittees (see above). However, consultations within the vaccination planning subcommittee of the Operative Staff seem to have been much more limited compared to other fields. Business, NGOs or local governmental actors were not involved in deciding and implementing vaccination plans. Unlike what happened for more controversial measures such as lockdowns and closures, in the case of the vaccination policy, which was framed in an unambiguously positive light, the central government denied local governments 'any substantial role in the vaccination system despite their readiness and willingness to help' (Csehi, 2023). Beyond blame-shifting, local government initiatives were useful for central crisis management decisions as a testing ground for novel policies. Some municipalities such as Budapest were often the first to act in cases such as providing easily accessible testing or vaccinations or implementing stricter restrictions to contain the spread of the virus. The central government could wait and see for a short period to assess whether those initiatives were successful, often copying them at the national level afterwards. This arrangement characterized by a very limited delegation of competences and the flow of information, ideas, and resources being directed towards the central government instead of genuine interactivity can be understood as an instance of sham local autonomy.

Italy. In 2021, the Italian government organized the vaccination campaign in a highly centralised manner. Bolgherini and Lippi (2022) explain that this implied a "shift from the former cooperative governance (grounded in joint decision-making in the development of provisions and policies) towards a centralized governance (grounded in the leadership of the Prime Minister and an 'adhocracy') where the Regions had mostly an implementation rather than a more active decision-making role". The same scholars conclude that the new centralized governance implied no formal change at the institutional level and was determined by political reasons. The interviews also suggest that relations between the State and the Regional Governments were sometimes tense. Some of these tensions – interviewees report – are due to the consequences of the delays in vaccine procurement, which forced national authorities to constantly redefine the number of vaccines sent to each region.

The Netherlands. The vaccination programme in the Netherlands was managed through the same MLG arrangement described above under the section "pandemic management", established to support decision-making processes, especially during the initial phases of the crisis. The national government drafted the vaccination strategy. Within the national framework, the regional Health Services were responsible for executing the national policy and, on the regional level, collaborations emerged between the PHS and other public and private stakeholders to arrange vaccination venues.

Spain. Vaccination policy in Spain was also defined through vertical interactions between the national government and the regions. Formally, the central government had to set an overall strategy for vaccination and regional governments had to implement it. To define the vaccination strategy, a multidisciplinary taskforce was created which included members of the Ministry of Health, members of the Vaccination Committee, representatives of regional governments, members of professional and scientific associations, members of the Bioethical committee, members of the Carlos III Health Institute and National Institute of Occupational Safety and Health and several experts. This taskforce was created by the inter-territorial council of the National Health Service, which had to approve the reports of the taskforce. The Council was formed by the Spanish Ministry of Health, a member of the Cabinet and the health councillors of each region (which played a key role in all decisions taken during the pandemic; see above). Initiatives within the council were usually started by the national government, and interactions were highly formalised. Other ad hoc meetings between the Ministry of Health and the regions also took place to deal with specific problems.

Table 4. Governance relations related to the vaccination process.

	Type of governance relations	Venue or arrangement	Type of actors involved	Promoters / initiators	Formality of relations	Leadership / Steering of the venue	Institutionalised venue or informal venue	Pre-existing or new venues?	In line with overall structure of distributed competences?
Belgium	Vertical relations	Arrangement	NG and RGs	Top-down	Unclear				Yes
Czechia	MLG	Arrangements	RGs, LGs, various nonpublic actors	Top-down (RGs)	Unclear				Yes
Denmark	MLG	Venue	Multistakeholder: NG, RGs, LGs, nonpublic actors	Top-down (NG)	Unclear	Top-down (NG)	Institutionalised	New	Yes
Estonia	MLG	Horizontal venue + vertical arrangement	NG + nonpublic actors; NG+ LGs;	Top-down	Horizontal venue: non-hierarchical; Vertical arrangement: hierarchical	(horizontal venue: bottom-up)	(horizontal venue: institutionalised)	(horizontal venue: new)	Yes
Hungary	High centralisation								Defies existing structures
Italy	High centralisation								Defies existing structures
Netherlands	MLG	Arrangement	LGs, safety regions, various nonpublic actors	Top-down	Hierarchical				Yes
Spain	MLG	MLG venue (created by a vertical venue)	NG, RGs, wide range of nonpublic actors	Top-down	Hierarchical	Top-down	Institutionalised	New	Yes

4.2. The role of MLG in responses to the refugee crisis.

This section aims to identify governance relations that emerged in the decision-making stage of the policy cycle during the refugee crisis in the eight EU countries analysed (see table 5 for the general overview). Insights provided in this section are derived from the country reports written by researchers of the ROBUST consortium in each country. Unlike in the case of the covid-19 crisis, no interview was conducted, and policy documents were the main source of information. Therefore, in many cases, information about the specific characteristics of the governance relations is not available. As for the covid-19 crisis, we specifically focus on national responses, and do not cover in this section subnational responses (i.e. responses that emerged in specific areas of the countries analysed, regardless of the governmental levels responsible for such actions). Furthermore, while management of the refugee crisis involved several different policy subfields we specifically focused on processes related to the organization of the reception system for asylum-seekers. For Eastern European countries the focus is on the more recent crisis related to the need to accommodate thousands of Ukrainian refugees since 2022. For the other countries the focus is on the so-called 2015 ‘European refugee crisis’.

Belgium. In Belgium a key role during the organization of responses to asylum-seekers’ reception during the refugee crisis was played by the government agency Fedasil, set up in 2001 exactly with the purpose of managing the accommodation and reception of asylum seekers. Since its establishment, Fedasil coordinated Local Accommodation Initiatives (LAIs) which are managed at the local level by the social services of the municipalities. With the rise in asylum-seeking flows in 2015, emergency reception centres were established by the federal level in buildings such as military bases, bungalow parks, boarding schools, and hospitals. In addition, more than 3,000 extra LAIs were established during 2015 and 2016. In order to open a LAI, the local governments can get in touch with the region with a proposal. The Region then would schedule a meeting with the local authorities and the regional coordinator (part of Fedasil). Once the proposal is accepted, Fedasil organizes quarterly consultation moments (regional meetings + learning networks) for the LAIs. This seems like a MLG venue that is top-down, vertical, and formal.

Czechia. Compared to 2014-2015, the Czech Republic reacted very promptly and positively towards the flow of Ukrainian migrants reaching the country in 2022. The reaction was both top-down and bottom-up, included all levels of public administration, citizens, NGOs and private organizations. The regional and local levels delivered most of needed services and responses (e.g., setting up regional assistance centres, organizing charities etc.), many of them based on own initiatives and resources. However, official venues that brought together all involved actors were not established. Some special bodies for evaluation and sharing of experiences were established. For instance, the Commission for Adaptation and Integration of Ukrainian refugees was established within the Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs. Associations of municipalities (the Union of Towns and Municipalities – SMOČR, or Association of Local Government – SMS) also tried to help, especially by providing information and guidance to municipalities and promoting the national programmes and grant schemes newly established.

Denmark. The Danish government negotiated agreements the municipalities and the national social partners to create an “employment-oriented” approach to refugee integration and a fair distribution of refugees across the country. The objective of this approach was to ensure that as many asylum recipients as possible would become self-supporting as quickly as possible (Gormsen 2016). The process that led to Danish responses to the refugee crisis – and specifically to its employment-oriented approach to reception and integration of asylum-seekers – had important multi-level and multi-sector aspects. In crafting the plan, the state worked actively with the municipalities as well the national employers’ and workers’ associations (specifically: the Confederation of Danish Employers (DA) and the Trade Union Federation (LO)). An important part of the plan was that partnerships between municipalities and local businesses would play a key role for enabling local implementation. To incentivize business participation, cash bonuses were included in the plan. In terms of governance process, the negotiation of the plan was coordinated by the Ministry of Employment (Gormsen 2016). It seems that no specific venue was created for these negotiations; yet it is clear that these (multi-level) conversations did take

place in one form or another. In any case, no MLG venue was publicly announced. It is safe to assume that negotiations took place in the usual venues for tripartite negotiations, deeply ingrained in all Danish decision-making, i.e., in government offices and the offices of the involved organizations. Such structure, while not corresponding to a formal venue, provides a set of routine channels for (formal or informal) interactions, by which a lot of things “get done” in Denmark. With this reform process, the government aimed to take the situation of municipalities into account. Likewise, the government sought to both harness private sector dynamism and pre-empt criticism from social partners by involving them directly in the design and implementation of the employment-centric approach. Companies especially were given a central role in taking on refugees as workforce and organizing occupation-oriented language training while efforts were made to avoid the refugee workforce undercutting collective agreements.

Estonia. Collaboration between different stakeholders was a key feature of Estonian responses to the increasing refugee flows to the country in 2014-2016. Meeting and collaboration were arranged involving the central Government, municipalities and civic organizations. As the local municipalities were a crucial actor in providing support services for the refugees, representatives of the leading ministries embarked on a two-week-long tour to all Estonian counties. Thus, the leading ministries created a forum to exchange and provide information to municipal governments. In fall of 2015, the Ministry of the Interior and Ministry of the Social Affairs created monthly meetings with agencies and relevant NGOs to discuss any issues and exchange information about the process. Prior to the crisis, the local governments had perceived the topic of refugees as a distant problem. The emergence of the crisis increased the municipalities sense of ownership to the challenge, as it was seen as a mutual issue that needed the joint efforts of stakeholders on all levels.

Hungary. During the European ‘refugee crisis’ the central government involved large humanitarian NGOs in the provision of services for refugees. These organizations were long-time partners of the government in service provision and mostly members of the Charitable Council – a consultation forum that involves the largest (mostly church-based) humanitarian organizations. According to anecdotal evidence, the government takes the input of Charitable Council into account as long as the organizations refrain from public criticism. However, it is unclear if this was the case during the refugee crisis in 2015. At the same time the government actively stigmatized and attacked critical NGOs, labelled them as ‘foreign agents’ (Gerő et al., 2023).

Italy. Italian responses to the 2015 refugee crisis were overseen by the so-called National Coordinating Group (or “Table”) on Asylum, which can be seen as an instance of MLG venue. This Group was a consultative working group created in 2015 by the national government as a venue for discussion and exchange on issues related to asylum-seekers’ reception among key stakeholders. Coordinated by the Department of Civil Liberties and Immigration of the Interior Ministry, the NCG included representatives of the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies, regional and local authorities (the Conference of the Regions, the Association of Italian Municipalities - ANCI, the Union of Italian Provinces), and representatives of key civil society organizations (Caritas and ARCI, which represented the National Asylum Roundtable of CSOs). UNHCR and the Ministry of Equal Opportunities were involved as invited members. The National Coordinating Group formally had merely consultative functions. Its specific tasks included coordinating national asylum policies, discussing potential improvements of the reception system, drafting a ‘reception and dispersal plan’ on an annual basis. De facto, the National Coordinating Group played an important role in shaping and reforming the Italian reception system. Proposals made within the National Coordinating Group were also discussed within Regional Working Groups on Asylum, similar bodies established with the purpose of coordinating and monitoring reception at the regional level. They included the Prefect of the regional capital (formally the head of the body), representatives of the other prefectures, of the regional government and of the regional branch of the ANCI. While CSOs were not formally involved in the Regional Groups, in some regions these were regularly consulted. In some regions, such as Emilia-Romagna and Tuscany, additional working tables were created between regional and local governments and CSOs, which led to the definition of regional standards for the operation of the reception system and other innovative solutions. The functioning of the working groups was regulated by an Agreement signed by the Unified Conference State-Regions-Local Authorities in 2014.

The Netherlands. Dutch responses to the refugee crisis were characterised by some horizontal relations. Organizations like the COA and the IND closely liaised with the Dutch government to provide accommodations for refugees. Municipalities also played a key role within the system for refugee reception: they could actively accommodate innovative initiatives and were responsible for housing and emergency shelter as well as concrete facilities. They also largely influenced national policies, as the prime minister and state secretary for asylum invited municipalities and provinces for consultation on the influx and reception of refugees during the crisis. Representatives of the Association of Dutch Municipalities and the Interprovincial Consultation were able to share their ideas and discuss necessary measures. According to the knowledge available these interactions aimed at improving decision-making did not involve nonpublic actors.

Spain. After some initiatives launched by the cities of Madrid and Barcelona, the Spanish government agreed to create an Inter-ministerial Commission which would coordinate the policies of the different ministries involved (Interior, Foreign Affairs, Defense, Health and Social Services, Justice and Education) and also agreed to convene the Sectoral Conference on Immigration, with representatives of the autonomous communities and the Spanish Federation of Municipalities and Provinces (FEMP). More broadly, the Spanish public sector actively engaged with CSOs and non-governmental actors to enhance the response to the refugee crisis. Platforms such as working groups, task forces, and consultative committees were established at the regional and local level to facilitate dialogue, partnership, and resource sharing. Interaction with CSOs were collaborative and non-hierarchical.

Table 5. Governance relations in response to the refugee crisis.

	Type of governance relations	Venue or arrangement	Type of actors involved	Promoters / initiators	Formality of relations	Leadership / Steering of the venue	Institutionalised venue or informal venue	Pre-existing or new venues?	In line with overall structure of distributed competences?
Belgium	MLG	Venue	Mainly intergovernmental: RGs, LGs; possibly some non-public actors	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	Yes
Czechia	MLG	Arrangement	NG, LGs, non-public actors	n.a.	n.a.				Yes
Denmark	MLG	Arrangement	NG, LGs, nonpublic actors	n.a.	n.a.				Yes
Estonia	MLG	Arrangement	NG+LG; NG+non-public actors	Top-down	Mixed				Yes
Hungary	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.				n.a.
Italy	MLG	Venue	Primarily intergovernmental - NG, RGs, LGs, nonpublic actors	Top-down	Hierarchical	Top-down	Institutionalised	New	Yes
Netherlands	Vertical relations	Venue	NG, LGs	Top-down	Hierarchical	Top-down	Institutionalised	New	Yes
Spain	Vertical relations	Venue	NGs, RGs, LGs	Bottom-up	n.a.	n.a.	Institutionalised	New	Yes

BOX 1. THE ROLE OF MLG IN RESPONSES TO RECENT CRISES IN A NON-EU COUNTRY: THE CASE OF NORWAY.

The covid crisis. For the period from the outbreak of the pandemic in early 2020 to March 2021, Christensen et al. (2022) find that crisis management in Norway was characterized by “by a general strengthening of the central government apparatus and hierarchical steering and coordination from the top” (p. 11). Structured governance relations on the vertical dimension of policymaking were very scarce, the authors find, while ad hoc arrangements and informal daily meetings between actors within the cabinet became important. As examples of such arenas that became important, Christensen et al. 2022 mention the Covid-19 committee within the cabinet, informal daily meetings between the Minister of Health (MH), the Norwegian Directorate of Health (ND) and the Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH), and an expert colloquium between NDH, NIPH and the health enterprises. A strong internal collaboration within the central government apparatus was furthermore supplemented by consultation with stakeholders and external expert advice. Yet, such network arrangements functioned “in the shadow of the hierarchy”, meaning that the “governance arrangement was characterized by governance informed by experts, rather than governance by experts” (Christensen et al 2022). As local governments were not involved in these arrangements, this does not qualify as an MLG venue. Some horizontal governance relations seem to have emerged in Norway in relation to the activities of the Directorate of Health, which established early contact with voluntary organizations. On 6 March 2020, the directorate invited a meeting with the three voluntary organizations that had emergency preparedness agreements with municipalities (the Norwegian Red Cross, the Norwegian Women’s Public Health Organization and Norwegians People Aid). These humanitarian organizations put in place many measures during the pandemic. Volunteers from The Norwegian women's public health organization assisted as emergency guards at health institutions and corona test stations. They delivered food and medicine and maintained social contact with people in home quarantine or home isolation. Some also produced infection control equipment. Norwegian People's Aid also contributed with various tasks. Among other things, they transported food to people in isolation or quarantine and worked with information related to ferries and aviation. (...) Regarding civil-society centric approaches, Arnesen and Sivesind (2021) show that voluntary organizations cooperated with authorities on a central level to a larger degree than on the local level. At both local and national levels voluntary organizations contributed to spreading information both to their member, but national organizations also took a larger role in providing information beyond their own members. In particular, minority organizations played an important role in conveying information in minority languages.

The Ukrainian refugee crisis. In Norway, the crisis led to a great commitment to help and good cooperation across the administration” (Digdir 2024). This cooperation scheme entailed facilitating collaboration and cooperation between actors at various levels concerning problem solving and policy making related to the deliver fast and effective measures to refugees arriving from Ukraine. An interesting MLG digital venue emerged in Norway related to the responses to the Ukrainian refugee crisis. Several actors – including the Norwegian Directorate of Immigration (UDI), The Directorate of Integration and Diversity (IMDi), the Norwegian Association of Local and Regional Authorities (KS) and municipalities, the Norwegian Tax Agency, the Norwegian Labour and Welfare Administration (NAV), the Norwegian Digitalisation Agency (Digdir) – held weekly dialogue meetings to coordinate of responses. In such meetings collaborations and preparation for the crisis were discussed. Civil society organizations were not involved in these networks, but corporate partners from private companies in different sectors in the labour market were involved. A number of interesting MLG venues seem to have emerged also at the local level, in various towns. In some localities, crisis teams were established, consisting of leaders of municipal service areas, modelled after what was considered successful practice in response to the Covid19 crisis. Such crisis teams held regular meetings, both physical meetings and Teams-meetings where they coordinated the efforts of partners response to the crisis in the municipality. New collaborations with volunteer organizations were also activated (e.g., Red Cross, local, The Norwegian Tourist Association), which were however mostly related to policy implementation.

4.3. The role of MLG in responses to the financial crisis

As part of the ROBUST project, country teams have also explored governance responses to the financial crisis in the eight EU countries analysed. As for the refugee crisis, this work did not imply the conduct of interviews and only relied on secondary sources. Our findings suggest that in some countries some horizontal relations emerged – involving national governments and their agencies and nonpublic actors (mostly private associations representing the banking sector and occasionally trade unions and employers' organizations). For example, in Belgium, during the financial crisis, after failures in negotiations on wage increases between employers and trade unions in the Central Council of Trade and Industry, the federal government stepped in. The government consulted social partners – and particularly the so-called 'group of ten' consisting of the most important negotiators of the federal social partners and including an equal number of representatives of trade unions and employee organizations – and such consultations played a key role in decision-making. Some of the measures adopted – such as the extension of the temporary unemployment measure to nonmanual workers – was originally proposed by the group of ten. Conversely, in none of the countries examined lower-level governments were ever involved in key decision-making processes. The only exception in this trend was represented by Belgium, where a vertical venue emerged, strictly linked to the country's peculiar institutional structure. Following forecasts of a substantial economic decline in 2009 and zero growth in 2010, and increases in unemployment in 2009 and 2010, the federal and regional governments drafted their own separate economic recovery plans, but all levels of government consulted and co-ordinated through an official standing body – the so-called 'consultative committee'. The committee, chaired by the Prime Minister, played a key role in defining Belgium's responses to the financial crisis, and took decisions by consensus. In addition to the federal Prime Minister, it included five federal ministers, the prime minister plus another minister of the Flemish regional government, the prime ministers of the Walloon regional government and of the French-speaking community, the prime minister of the Brussels government plus another minister from another language group, and the prime minister of the German-speaking community.

5. The role of MLG in responses to recent crises at the EU level.

Which kind of governance relations emerged at the EU level at the decision-making stage of the policy cycle, in relation to responses to recent crises? As part of the ROBUST fieldwork, we collected extensive secondary sources on governance relations during the pandemic crisis and refugee crisis at the EU level. For the refugee crisis we could also rely on extensive interviews conducted on MLG as part of the MiNMUS project (see Caponio 2022). Our analysis suggests that, overall, some MLG dynamics emerged particularly in the framework of the refugee crisis, while management of the pandemic crisis was largely characterised by the emergence of intergovernmental relations involving the European Commission and national governments. An extensive analysis of EU decision-making processes during both crises was done by Bojar and Kriesi (2023), in a well-cited piece that aims to reconstruct 'decision-making structures in the EU under crisis conditions to shed new light on the role played by supranational actors, governments of member states and other types of actors' (p. 428), and by Blauburger et al. (2022) in an article that focuses specifically on governance interactions and actors' participation in decision-making during the pandemic.

The covid-19 crisis.

Bojar and Kriesi (2023) suggest that decision-making processes during the pandemic crisis largely involved coordination between national governments and the European Commission concerning, among the various issues, border control measures, public health measures (including social distancing rules,

stay-at-home requirements, closures and openings of institutions, and other related measures), economic measures in the regulatory and monetary sphere (including issues related to state aid), fiscal policy measures with the NGEU Fund debate in the centre and institutional measures (such as emergency powers). Only in the case of monetary policies and the management of borders responses were related to areas of EU competence. In the case of vaccine procurement, the European Commission also played a key role, despite this being an area not previously under its own competences (which might be seen as an example of adaptive or innovative response at the EU level). Blauburger et al. (2022) distinguish among the three areas of borders, health and welfare. In the policy area of borders, the EU Commission mainly supervised exceptions to Schengen Border Code. In the field of health the Commission and regulatory agencies played a very limited coordinative role in pure public health (see also Brooks et al. 2023). In the area of welfare, the authors mainly observed transgovernmental coordination by the Administrative Commission on the Coordination of Social Security Systems.

Our analysis of secondary sources suggests that no MLG venue emerged at the EU level in the context of decision-making processes related to all these areas. In early 2020, the Presidency of the Council activated the EU's integrated political crisis response mechanism (IPCR), a pre-existing arrangement chaired by the Council that informally coordinates EU institutions, member states and additional relevant actors such as the EU agency "European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control" (Blauburger et al. 2022; see also: Hollis, 2020; Russack & Fenner, 2020, p. 7). Based on the information available nonpublic actors (as also local governments) were not involved in this intergovernmental venue. In 2020 the European Commission also established another informal network – the so-called 'COVID-19 Information Group - Home Affairs' or 'DG Home Group'. During the first wave of the pandemic, the network held weekly meetings together with various DGs and member state representatives. Anecdotal evidence reported by Blauburger et al. (2022) suggests that private companies were occasionally consulted in order to share information and best practices. The network however largely discussed border controls, and such discussions mainly involved the Commission and member states.

Additional interesting decision-making fora – which however qualifies more as a knowledge interface and not as a governance venue according to the definition adopted in this report (see sections 1 and 2 above) were the Health Security Committee, composed by health experts of member states, which became a key source of information for the Commission and a crucial institution to coordinate national responses (Deruelle & Engeli, 2021, p. 1376), and the Vaccine Steering Board (see Blauburger et al. 2022).

Blauburger et al. report that after some months the Commission made an effort to merge these different fora into one venue. The authors report that 'the IPCR seemed the most plausible institution to coordinate the COVID-19 pandemic, since response measures cut across different policy areas and the competences affected (mainly borders, public security, health and welfare) remained in the hands of member states' (Blauburger et al. 2022 p. 705). No further information have been retrieved however about the operation of the IPCR in the second pandemic wave.

Overall, Blauburger and colleagues draw the following conclusions about governance relations emerged at the EU level during the covid-19 pandemic:

Vertical transgovernmental networks bringing EU and national actors together were essential in managing the early response to the COVID-19 crisis. Two trends are worth underlining: first, those networks that existed previously (Administrative Commission and IPCR) were more successful in becoming focal points, which shows that similar backgrounds and previous cooperation helps to provide a more efficient and coordinated response to the crisis. In contrast, the absence of a clear focal point in the area of health provided better chances for the Commission to orchestrate a common response at the EU level (cf. Brooks et al., 2023). Second, there are limitations to the work of transgovernmental networks, especially when solutions require stepping out of a coordination problem and into a distributive one (Blauburger et al. 2022, p. 709).

The refugee crisis.

In the case of the refugee crisis, Bojar and Kriesi (2023) identify, as the key areas of EU involvement in key governance processes, those of border control, redistribution of asylum seekers, asylum-seekers' reception and the reform of the EU's asylum regime. The two authors mainly focus on intergovernmental processes that took place, particularly in the area of border control and redistribution of asylum-seekers. An interesting MLG venue at the EU level, however, emerged in the context of the so-called Urban Agenda for the EU, adopted by the Dutch Presidency of the EU Council on May 30, 2016 with the so-called "Pact of Amsterdam" which was signed by all the ministers responsible for urban matters in the twenty-seven EU member countries.

As specified by the "Pact of Amsterdam," the UAEU had the goal of engaging urban authorities in achieving "Better Regulation, Better Funding and Better Knowledge" by offering a new form of multilevel and multi-stakeholder cooperation (Council of the European Union 2016, 3). At the same time, though, the UAEU was characterised as a legally non-binding process and no specific funds were allocated for its implementation (Council of the European Union 2016, 5). As underlined by interviews conducted as part of the MiNMUS project, a key role in the preparation of the UAEU was played by officials of the Dutch Ministry of the Interior. In this context, it was decided to establish a specific 'Partnership on the Inclusion of Migrants and Refugees' (PIMR). The Mayor of Amsterdam agreed to assume the role of chair and Dimitris Avramopoulos, then the EU Commissioner for Migration, Home Affairs and Citizenship, was invited to co-chair.

The composition of the PIMR clearly reflected the key role of local governments and EC representatives. With respect to the former, the PIMR included representatives of the Working Group on Migration and Integration of Eurocities; the mayors of Athens, Barcelona, Berlin and Helsinki; the Council of European Municipalities and Regions (CEMR); as well as the Committee of the Regions and the Urbact Programme. As for the EC, along with DG Home, two more DGs were involved—DG Regional and Urban Policies (DG Region) and DG Employment, Social Affairs & Inclusion (DG Empl)—together with the Joint Research Centre and other European institutions like the Council of Europe Development Bank (CEB) and the European Investment Bank (EIB). Furthermore, the PIMR included four representatives from EU member states, that is, Denmark, Greece, Italy and Portugal; of Brussels-based think tanks like the European Council for Refugees and Exiles (ECRE) and the Migration Policy Group (MPG). NGOs and migrant associations were engaged through specific work conferences.

As is clear, the vertical or intergovernmental dimension of policy-making processes was central in the PIMR experience. However, the agenda-setting phase was characterised by a more inclusive and open approach, which aimed to engage a large number of stakeholders from NGOs, CSOs and immigrant associations through various work conferences. In other words, a broad consultation process took place on the results of the preliminary studies on the bottlenecks to integration carried out by MPG and on the draft of the Action Plan of the PIMR. This latter document incorporated some of the key feedback provided by non-governmental actors in the work conferences, such as that of taking into account immigrants' and refugees' perspectives in policy-making, which led to the creation of the European Migrant Advisory Board (EMAB) to incorporate migrants' perspective in policy-making processes.

Other actions such as those led by the EIB on financial blending and microfinance, or that on access to EU funding led by Eurocities, while certainly addressing important issues with respect to ensuring a "better funding" of urban policies, seem to reflect more longstanding agendas of the leader organisations. Eurocities for instance, has always been active in lobbying for local authorities' direct access to EU funding, and this topic became even more salient in the context of the 2015 refugee crisis.

If during agenda-setting the horizontal dimension regarding relations with non-public actors gained relevance, the implementation of the Action Plan again brought the vertical/intergovernmental dimension to the fore, especially in terms of relations between the European Commission and local/regional authorities. In principle, national authorities were also expected to engage in the implementation of the actions identified by the PIMR, leading to the emergence of tripartite collaborative

relationships. However, representatives of the four countries participating in the PIMR, that is, Denmark, Greece, Portugal and Italy, contributed only to a limited extent to the implementation of the Action Plan, as acknowledged in the final evaluation report (Heimann and Stürner 2019, 22). With respect to the horizontal dimension, the role of non-public actors seems to have been particularly relevant in the implementation of only a few action. More specifically, NGOs were engaged in the action on unaccompanied minors; immigrant associations and a private foundation like OSF in that on the establishment of the EMAB; while private think tanks contributed to various actions, assuming a leadership role in that on urban indicators. In general, according to the final evaluation report, the strategy of some of the PIMR's working groups was "of reaching out" to external actors in a "needs-oriented way," that is, to incorporate specific expertise and broaden the PIMR's operational network without adding complexity to the basic structure (Heimann and Stürner 2019).

6. MLG in crises: some emerging hypotheses

This section aims to put insights articulated in the previous sections together and generate some hypotheses on the drivers of the emergence of MLG relations in decision-making processes about responses to crises.

Table 6 below provides a general overview of governance relations that emerged in the eight EU countries and the three crises analysed in this report. The following patterns emerge from the table and the analysis conducted in the previous sections.

First, different types of governance relations emerged in the countries analysed in response to different types of crises. MLG relations emerged more consistently, across most countries, in the context of the refugee crises. Conversely, in the case of the financial crisis, involvement of both subnational governments and nonpublic actors in decision-making was extremely limited as responses were highly centralised at the national level. In the case of the pandemic crisis, a mixed picture emerged from our analysis: horizontal and vertical relations emerged in a non-homogeneous way, only in some countries and in relation to decisions related to some of the specific areas analysed (vaccinations, school closures and the overall pandemic management). Overall, more MLG relations emerged in the case of responses related to vaccination campaigns (and, to a more limited extent, school closures), while MLG was much rarer in the case of decisions related to the overall pandemic management. This latter area was characterised by highly centralised responses in most countries, and by the emergence of vertical relations, particularly in those (federal or semifederal) countries where subnational governments had key competences in the health policy field. As to decisions related to school closures, these were more often characterised by the emergence of horizontal governance relations between governments and nonpublic actors compared to the two other areas.

Interestingly, no clear pattern emerges from Table 6 in terms of variation in governance relations across different countries. On the one hand, and not surprisingly, it is true that vertical relations seem to have emerged more frequently in federal and semi federal countries. On the other hand, in none of the countries analysed MLG arrangements or venues emerged across all of the three policy areas analysed related to the covid-19 pandemic. Three of the analysed countries (Estonia, Netherlands, and Spain) were characterised by MLG relations in two of the three policy areas, while in four countries MLG relations emerged in only one policy area (Czechia, Denmark, Hungary, Italy). Only in Belgium no MLG relations emerged in any of the three policy areas. Remarkably, in some countries responses in two areas were characterised by a high centralisation but an MLG venue emerged in the third policy area: this is, for instance, the case of Denmark, where an MLG venue emerged related to the organization of the vaccination campaign.

Table 6. Overview of governance relations in the three crises analysed.

	<i>Pandemic Management</i>	<i>School Closures</i>	<i>Vaccination Campaigns</i>	<i>Refugee Crisis</i>	<i>Financial Crisis</i>
<i>Belgium</i>	Vertical venues	Horizontal venue	Vertical arrangement	MLG venue	MLG arrangement
<i>Czechia</i>	Centralisation	Centralisation	MLG arrangements	MLG arrangement	Centralisation
<i>Denmark</i>	Centralisation (with limited vertical consultations)	Centralisation	MLG venue	MLG arrangement	Centralisation
<i>Estonia</i>	Vertical arrangement	MLG (horizontal arrangement + vertical venue)	MLG (horizontal venue + vertical arrangement)	MLG arrangement	Centralisation
<i>Hungary</i>	MLG Venue (but rarely both dimensions present at the same time)	Horizontal venues (sparse)	Centralisation	Unclear	Centralisation
<i>Italy</i>	Vertical venue	MLG (horizontal arrangement + vertical venue)	Centralisation	MLG venue	Centralisation
<i>The Netherlands</i>	MLG arrangement	Centralisation	MLG Arrangement	Vertical venue	Centralisation
<i>Spain</i>	Vertical venue	MLG venue	MLG venue (created by a vertical venue)	Vertical venue	Centralisation

It is also interesting to look specifically at the kind of MLG arrangements and venues that emerged in response to crises in the eight EU countries analysed. Our analysis suggests that, in the case of responses to the pandemic crisis, the vast majority of the venues identified were created and managed top-down by higher level governments, were highly institutionalised, and mostly aligned with institutional structures. More variation can be observed in relation to the hierarchical or non-hierarchical nature of interactions within venues: in the case of venues dealing with the overall pandemic management, relations were always highly hierarchical, while in the case of school closures and vaccination campaigns some of the venues were characterised by less hierarchical interactions. Interestingly, more than half of the venues identified were created *ad hoc* to coordinate responses to the analysed crises, while the remaining venues were set up before the crises and were exploited during the crises to coordinate policy responses. In the case of the refugee crisis, information available about the characteristics of the MLG venues is more limited, as already mentioned. However, it seems that, overall, some new venues were created as a result of bottom-up pressure of local authorities and nonpublic actors (e.g., in the case of Spain).

Finally, it is relevant to ask which factors seem to explain the variation observed so far in governance relations emerged in response to crises. In other words, which are the drivers of MLG relations during crises? While our analysis certainly does not allow to make definitive conclusions on this, it allows us to formulate several hypotheses, related to patterns and insights emerged in the cases observed.

A first key factor seems to be the scope, severity and urgency of the crisis. In several countries it seems that this factor contributes to explain the emergence of different types of governance relations. In times of utmost urgency, such as that of the immediate responses to the pandemic in March 2020, centralisation seems to prevail, and decisions were mostly taken at the highest governmental level. The analysis and interviews conducted suggest that centralisation in these instances is perceived to have two main advantages. On the one hand, the use of central authority allows governments to act more quickly (and possibly more efficiently) and to keep potential disagreements about the priorities of governmental action under control. On the other hand, citizens expect centralized leadership and are ready to accept it when things become extremely serious. With the passing of time, in situations of persistent turbulence but not of acute crisis, such as those that characterised the second part of 2020, horizontal and (more often) vertical governance relations emerged in several countries. For instance, in Spain and Italy, regional governments started to play a key role in pandemic management since the late spring 2020.

A second important factor that seems to explain variation in the emergence of governance relations in the cases analysed is, not surprisingly, pre-existing institutional structures. As expected, more governance relations emerged in situations and fields where subnational governments and nonpublic actors were already directly involved in policy making or policy implementation. For instance, vertical relations regularly emerged in federal and semi federal countries, particularly in areas of decentralised or shared competences among national and subnational governments. At the same time, and more specifically, venues seem to have emerged in cases where not only subnational actors and non-public actors played a key role in policymaking and/or policy implementation, but also in cases where structured consultations among these actors were absent, fractured or not effective. In other words, in countries characterised by institutionalised and/or regular and effective consultation mechanisms among the above-mentioned actors (e.g., Denmark), the creation of specific venues where actors met to discuss crisis responses was less needed. Conversely, in countries such as Italy, characterised by an often-chaotic dispersal of authority among the national government and regions and often tense relations among these actors, the need for specific venues where actors could discuss crisis responses became more urgent.

A third important factor was related to the degree of politicisation and polarisation of the policy issues at stake, at the level of both public opinion and political debates. In some instances, a low polarization seems to have legitimised and fostered centralised responses. For instance, during the first part of the pandemic, national governments in all countries benefitted from a broad societal support, a result of well-known 'rally around the flag' effects, which legitimised more centralised approaches. Governance relations, on both the horizontal and vertical dimension, seem to have emerged, in many countries, in situations in which the national government started to perceive criticism and opposition from subnational governments and nonpublic actors. For instance, the Spanish national government decided to involve regional governments in key decisions related to the pandemic management when starting to perceive some opposition from their side in late spring 2020. A similar dynamic applied to the case of Italy, where most regional governments were controlled by a different party coalition than the national government. Overall, relations between the State and Regions in Italy during the pandemic decisively 'changed according to the political climate' (Bolgherini and Lippi 2022). Finally, the case of Hungary suggests that involvement of local governments in key decision-making processes very much responded to and was linked to the government's political needs and attempts of blame-shifting in contexts characterised by high polarisation and societal opposition.

A fourth important driver of the emergence of MLG relations in decision-making processes in situations of crisis is related to previous experiences of crisis management. In the case of many of the responses analysed higher level policymakers seem to have activated governance relations following patterns that

had been established in previous crisis responses and particularly that had been perceived as successful in response to past crises. In other cases, governance relations emerged to avoid conflicts or inefficiencies that had characterised previous crises. An interesting case in this respect is that of Denmark's response to the refugee crisis, where local governments were involved in crisis responses with the aim (among the others) to avoid the emergence of conflicts as those that had emerged while responding to older refugee flows. In Czechia several public administrators from the local and the regional level interviewed as part of the ROBUST project reported that 'due to the COVID-19 pandemic we got used to more cooperation with various actors' and that 'the pandemic led to establishment and certain embeddedness of communication channels and direct communication with some actors which also helped coping with the refugee crisis following the war in Ukraine'.

PART 2: MLG AND ROBUSTNESS

7. Examining governance relations in selected cases of robust governance at the subnational level

In order to answer the second research question of this report – about the contribution of MLG interactivity on the robustness of governance responses – in this section we examine in depth 12 cases of robust governance responses in the eight EU countries analysed. Such cases were all selected because they were examples of robust governance responses i.e. responses characterised by innovativeness or adaptiveness which were widely considered legitimate (see deliverable on robustness D.2.1). All of our 12 cases focus on responses that were primarily developed at the regional or local level. In other words, these were responses in fields/areas in which local and regional governments were left some room for manoeuvre in establishing specific policies that complemented national policies or in implementing national guidelines that specified broad objectives to be reached.

Focusing on specific cases at the subnational level was assumed to be highly relevant in order to understand the links between MLG and robustness, as determining the (degree of) robustness of national responses to crises such as the ones described in the previous section was often quite challenging. In the subsections that follow we examine each of the 12 cases (see table 7 for an overview). First, we briefly describe the responses and explain why they can be seen as examples of robust responses (we only include key information here, but more extensive accounts of all these cases are available in ROBUST country reports). Then, we assess the horizontal and vertical governance relations that emerged in each of the cases, examining the same key features of governance arrangements or venues described in the previous section.

Case 1 (Belgium): ELZs and contact tracing. This case examines a local contact tracing initiative in several cities in the Flanders region, which can be seen as a remarkable illustration of adaptation during the pandemic crisis. In September 2020 the Flemish government assigned the task of local contact tracing to the *Eerstelijnszones* (ELZs), i.e., networks composed of primary healthcare providers, representatives from local authorities, insurance companies, user associations, and experts. Being responsible for a certain zone in the city, each ELZ possesses extensive local knowledge and trust from its residents – all essential advantages in the case of contact tracing. These activities were financially supported by the regional government, and developed in consultation with the *Agentschap Zorg en Gezondheid*, COVID-19 teams, and the contact tracing consortium. GPs were in fact concerned that the contact tracing approach developed in a centralized manner was not going to be efficient, given the language barriers, mistrust, and inability to investigate certain groups – all problems that they have encountered and have knowledge about. This initiative seems to be characterised by the emergence of an MLG venue which was top-down (as it was established by the Flemish government), multistakeholder, institutionalised (the ELZs have formalized structures, for example each has a Health Council that guides the activities) but characterised by a high informality of interactions (the mode of interaction within the ELZ is reported to have been not highly formalized, as they were reacting to local circumstances with their available resources quite quickly).

Case 2 (Czechia) – Vaccination in Brno. This case focuses on the vaccination campaign in the city of Brno, where the first large-scale vaccination centre in Czechia was created by the Jihomoravský region (in close cooperation with the city, its political leadership and executive) and opened at the exhibition site which was operated by the city organization BVV Trade Fairs Brno (i.e., city enterprise, a joint stock company owned by the city Brno). Interviews suggest that this was a robust response: the opening of this big centre is an example of innovative solution, implementation was highly successful and the initiative was perceived as highly legitimate, and this experience was used as an exemplary practice that inspired other local initiatives in other Czech cities. Interestingly, a temporary emergency hospital had been previously established in one of the pavilions and opened in the beginning of November 2020

based on close cooperation between the city (their mayor, usually employees of departments for crisis management, healthcare and finance participated during discussions also), hospitals (their management) and the region (president and employees from the city executive – again especially from the departments for healthcare, crisis management and finance). According to the interview material both initiatives were the outcome of discussions involving all of the above-mentioned actors. While information about how these discussions took place are limited, interviews conducted suggest that actors discussed among them different emergency scenarios and plans for action.

Case 3 (Czechia): crisis committees. This case focuses on regional crisis committees that were created in many Czech regions and dealt with key decisions about the management of lockdowns, opening and closures of economic activities, testing and tracing. This case can be considered robust as it led to the development of adaptive measures in various regions which were not contested in most cases. As mentioned earlier the national Czech pandemic management was highly centralised and top-down. Regions had to implement national guidelines and were required by legislation to coordinate the crisis management response in their territories. In doing so they had to cooperate with municipalities which had important responsibilities on various issues. In this framework, crisis committees of both regions and cities were important venues established by regional and local executives where governmental and nongovernmental actors gathered. The committees did not formally have decision-making powers (decisions were formally made by regional and local executives) but played a key role in decision-making. The committees existed before the crisis. The interviews indicate that the composition of people participating in these platforms varies during the pandemic and often reflected the topic that was being discussed. Overall, their composition and scope varied with the passing of time, and they included permanent and temporary members. Key de facto permanent members in crisis committees were members of the local/regional executive. Most meetings were also attended by members of the city board and representatives of other organizations like hospitals or public health authority. Often representatives of municipal/city offices participated in the meetings of regional crisis committees and representatives of the regional public health office often attended meetings of city crisis committees. New members joined the meeting ad hoc, such as representatives of the social services, representatives of territorial departments of police or fire brigade, heads of hospitals, health insurance funds, NGOs etc. When the crisis committees discussed about vaccinations, professional associations of GPs were involved in the discussions. Increase in the number of members over time seem to reflect growing uncertainty and fear about how the pandemic developed. Overall, these crisis committees qualify as institutionalised MLG venues which were created and managed top-down, were primarily intergovernmental in terms of their membership.

Table 7. Interactivity and MLG venues in selected cases of robust governance at the subnational level.

Case of robust governance	Policy area	Level	Type of governance relations	Venue or arrangement	Type of actors involved	Promoters / initiators	Formality of relations	Leadership / Steering of the venue	Institutionalised venue or informal venue	Pre-existing or new venues?	In line with overall structure of distributed competences?
Case 1 (Belgium)	Pandemic management (contact tracing)	Local	MLG	Venue	Multistakeholder (very limited involvement of NG)	Top-down	Non-hierarchical	Local actors	Institutionalized	Pre-existing	Yes
Case 2 (Czechia)	Vaccination in Brno	Regional	Vertical relations	Venue	Intergovernmental (LG, RG)	Top-down (RG)	Non-hierarchical	Unclear	Institutionalised	Unclear	Yes
Case 3 (Czechia)	Pandemic management	Regional and Local	MLG	Venues (regional/local)	LG, RG, nonpublic actors	Top-down (RG/LG)	Hierarchical	RG/LG	Institutionalized	Pre-existing	Yes
Case 4 (Denmark)	Vaccination	Local	MLG	Arrangement + horizontal venue	LG, religious groups, nonpublic actors, NG	LG	Hierarchical	LG	Informal	New	Yes
Case 5 (Hungary)	Schools (roma communities)	Local	Horizontal relations	Venue	Limited multistakeholder (NGO, public actors (SLB))	Bottom-up (NGO)	Non-hierarchical	NGO	Informal	New	Non-public initiative to compensate gaps in public responses
Case 6 (Italy)	Pandemic management (PPE in prisons)	Local	MLG	Venue	Intergovernmental (NG, heads of prisons, private companies)	Top-down (NG)	Non-hierarchical	NG	Informal (zoom meeting)	New	Yes
Case 7 (Italy)	Refugee crisis (Tuscany)	Regional	MLG	Venue	Multistakeholder (RG, LGs, nonpublic actors)	Top-down (RG)	Non-hierarchical	RG	Informal physical venue	New	Challenges existing division of competences
Case 8 (Netherlands)	Schools (Utrecht)	Local	Horizontal relations	Venue	LG, SLBs, private actors, civil society	Unclear	Non-hierarchical	Unclear	Informal	Partially pre-existent	Initiative beyond national guidelines
Case 9 (Netherlands)	Vaccination (Rustic Haven)	Local	Horizontal relations (but only in the second phase)	Unclear	Practitioners, nonpublic actors, national health agency	Bottom-up (Practitioners and nonpublic actors)	Unclear				Initiative beyond national guidelines
Case 10 (Netherlands)	Vaccination (Urk)	Local	Vertical relations + key role of practitioner	Venue	Practitioners, LG, national health agency	Bottom-up (Practitioners)	Non-hierarchical	LG	Informal	New	Initiative beyond national guidelines
Case 11 (Netherlands)	Refugee crisis (Plan Einstein)	Local	MLG	Venue	Multistakeholder (LG, nonpublic actors, minor role of NG)	Bottom-up (Local alliance public-nonpublic)	Non-hierarchical	LG	Formalised due to participation in EU project (but no formal body)	New	Initiative beyond national guidelines
Case 12 (Spain)	Vaccination (Aragón)	Regional	MLG	Arrangement	Intergovernmental	Top-down (RG)	Hierarchical				Yes

Case 4 (Denmark): vaccination in Ishøj. This case concerns the way in which the vaccination campaign was handled in Ishøj municipality during 2020 and 2021. Ishøj one of the most challenged municipalities in Denmark in terms of corona incidents. The municipality has the highest number of immigrants and descendants of immigrants in Denmark, around 50% and many of these migrants were quite worried about the possible side-effects of the vaccines, which made promotion quite difficult. Following a rise in incident rates in February 2021, the Ministry of Health decided that a series of strengthened measures had to be adopted in Ishøj. The municipality was called to implement the regulations and deal with the specific circumstances. Four decisions taken by the municipal Crisis Staff – in collaboration with other municipal actors - proved particularly important. Firstly, Ishøj municipality decided to establish a second site of testing and vaccination in the Cultural Centre to boost test and vaccination rates. Secondly, there was a big task in communicating to citizens where and how testing and vaccination was to be done. Here housing associations, Imams and streetworkers were instrumental in identifying suitable sites for mobile pop-up testing and vaccination facilities. Thirdly, a plan had to be drawn up for ongoing tests of care staff in the eldercare sector. Here the head of the health centre and the head of the eldercare services were very important. Fourthly, vaccination of citizens in the nursing homes was planned. The response was not fully effective in boosting vaccination but was still quite robust as it allowed to produce viable solutions under unfavorable conditions, strong skepticism against vaccination. Moreover, the response managed to uphold core public services and curbing disease spread and mortality via fundamental adaptations and innovations that adhered to core public values of democratic legitimacy. The key decision-making arena was the municipal crisis staff. Decisions were made based on discussions between the members of the crisis staff, who in turned got feedback every single day from their employees working in direct contact with housing associations, schools, eldercare, businesses, etc. Several stakeholders played a role in securing testing and vaccination. The Crisis Staff together with four or five temporary groups on protective equipment (mask, disinfectant), on eldercare service, on schools, and on housing associations were crucial stakeholders as they had often unique access to important target populations (the old, the children, the ethnic minorities, etc.). These groups were all made up by municipal directors and key employees. While private or social partners were not directly involved in the discussions of the crisis staff, the groups had close contact with many private and social actors in the municipality to be able to ensure testing and vaccination. Apart from the daily meetings in the crisis staff, the venues for coordination and knowledge-sharing were the frequent physical or online (Teams/Zoom) meetings 1) between the crisis staff and the members of the groups listed above, and 2) between the members of the groups and municipal employees, school students and their parents, apartment block dwellers, and the members of the Turkish and Pakistani religious communities. Coordination between the municipality on the one hand, and the region and the national health authorities on the other mainly took the form of a one-directional avenue of regulations, guidelines and information flowing from the state and the region to the municipality. However, several heads and employees from Ishøj municipality were in close dialogue with the Region on how best organize testing and vaccination in order to increase testing and vaccination rates. While there was no permanent formal forum for these vertical relations, the communication and cooperation on the issue of testing and vaccination on the vertical dimension took place more or less constantly from autumn 2020 to summer 2022. Overall, this case therefore represents an example of MLG arrangement, within which a specific horizontal venue was created, which however did not involve actors from higher level of government.

Case 5 (Hungary): Schooling and Roma communities. The focal topic of this case study lies in the intersection of two crises: the acute crack-down of the pandemic and the resulting distancing and lockdown measures on Hungary's school system on one hand, and the chronic crisis of schooling Hungary's Roma children, especially those living in socio-economically strongly disadvantaged and segregated localities, on the other. It specifically focuses on a village located in a disadvantaged region of Eastern Hungary (anonymized), where a specific robust response was developed to provide ethnic Roma children – suffering from multiple forms of socio-economic, educational and cultural disadvantages and discrimination – with extra-curricular education

support. The initiative was developed first and foremost by a national-level NGO (hereinafter: Foundation), in cooperation with public institutional actors, the local public school, local social workers and the family support service. The response can be seen as characterised by horizontal relations involving public and non-public actors. Relations seem not to have developed in a structured body/forum but were reported to be very frequent and systematic. This case therefore can be seen as an example of an informal venue, started and coordinated by a local NGO.

Case 6 (Italy): Production of PPE in prisons. This case concerns the production of personal protective equipment (PPE) in Italian prisons – and particularly in the cities of Milan, Naples and Palermo – during the first wave of the pandemic. This was a robust response due to its innovative character, and its long-term goals of setting up an initiative that, besides responding to the urgent need for (highly scarce) PPE in Spring 2020, was designed to inspire further training programmes within Italian prisons aimed at facilitating prisoners' inclusion in the labour market. The initiative was highlighted by the United Nations as an example of a 'good practice' in prison policy. The development of the initiative was coordinated by a sort of online task force. The leading role was taken by the Office for Socially Useful Work of the Department of Prison Administration of the Ministry of Justice. The interviews suggest that the whole initiative originated from discussions involving also the Extraordinary Commissioner for the Implementation of Health Measures to Contain the COVID-19 pandemic. The task force included 12-13 people. The online coordination tables were attended by representatives of the private companies involved in the initiative, and representatives of the prisons where the production sites were established. According to the interviews, no representatives of local and regional governments have been ever involved in the coordination tables. The interviews conducted suggest that, on the one hand, the relatively high number of institutions and actors involved in the response – and specifically actors with different competences – was crucial for its success. On the other hand, some interviewees underlined that this also increased the complexity of the decision-making and implementation process. Other interviewees highlighted the fact that the leading role of the public authorities was crucial. Another interviewee highlighted that the success of the initiative was first and foremost related to the good will, availability, creativity and passion of individual persons, and the collaboration between these individual persons, more than to their institutions and organizations. This individual commitment was crucial to overcome several challenges related to the functioning of public administration and its bureaucratic procedures. Overall, this response was characterised by the emergence of a top-down, informal a primarily intergovernmental MLG venue.

Case 7 (Italy): the Tuscan reception system. This case concerns the development of a specific, innovative, and highly effective reception system in the Italian region of Tuscany during the 2015 refugee crisis (see Pettrachin 2022). The initiative was the result of quite visible multilevel governance processes, i.e. relatively self-organized interactions between interdependent public and private actors at different levels and scales and also across these levels and scales. Key decisions were the outcome of collaborations between local governments and regional governments, with a decisive involvement of non-governmental organizations (among them: ARCI, Caritas, Oxfam). The MLG interactions were not structured by formal and constitutional rules but rather by a flexible and adaptable ad hoc design. On the vertical dimension, the interactions involved the local and regional levels, but not the national level. On the contrary, the interviews conducted suggest that relations between Tuscan regional and local authorities and national authorities (including the national government) were highly conflictual throughout the whole 'refugee crisis'. Many interviewees suggest that the development of this robust policy response was facilitated by the fact that the actors involved had similar political ideologies (the local and regional governments involved were all from centre-left parties and they relied on established patterns of cooperation with left-wing or progressive Catholic civil society organizations).

Case 8 (The Netherlands): schools in Utrecht. This case focuses on decisions made at the local level, in the city of Utrecht in the Netherlands, about how to implement national guidelines on school closures and reopening. While, as mentioned in the previous section, decisions in this

policy area were made hierarchically and in a top-down manner in the Netherlands, at the local level, actors had to make sense of rules. More specifically, this case focuses on the robust case of one specific school within the city of Utrecht where innovative solutions were developed and that performed unexpectedly well. In former research during the first lockdown, the *Werkplaats Onderwijs* *Onderzoek Utrecht-Gelijke Onderwijskansen* (Educational Research Utrecht-Equal Educational Opportunities) conducted research together with ten primary schools in Utrecht into the impact of the first school closure on pupils' learning growth in terms of mathematics and reading comprehension (Henrichs et al., 2021). This study identified one school – called "Harmony Grove Primary" – that showed increased performance in math and reading, even though other schools' performances declined. Decisions that led to the development of these responses were made in the context of many online meeting arenas where different actors could consult with each other. Different stakeholders, like the municipality, youth care, child care services, but also the schools and directors, voluntary organizations and sometimes even private actors like banks met in round table conversations during the school closures. A core group of existing partners formed the decision-making body, while new partners (such as banks) were brought in for specific issues like laptop provision. For a part, new partners came to the table, but for the most part these were already existing arenas (like the Utrechtse Onderwijs Agenda (UOA) which were broadened. These new 'extended tables' did not have any formal names, they just emerged. Decisions were made with much deliberation and consensus. According to respondents, there was no partner that had more power than the others. The involved actors in deliberation about the local response were only actors of the level of the municipality. There was interaction between levels of government in a vertical top-down way, from the minister and the ministry of Health down to the municipality. No representative or staff of higher-level institutions was involved in decision-making processes, and local actors had no chance to be included in arenas or tables with higher level actors (or other local actors from other municipalities) where they could share their local perspective on the matter. Interviews suggest that local actors perceived national decisionmakers as being closed in an ivory tower in which rules were made that needed to be made workable by the professional on the ground by changing the rules or sometimes even ignoring the rules.

Case 9 (The Netherlands): vaccination promotion in Rustic Haven. This case presents a highly innovative and effective local vaccination strategy developed in the neighbourhood of *Rustic Haven* (fictional name), a district of a large, multi-ethnic Dutch city (+/- 700.000 inhabitants), known for its diverse community and creative scene, but also for the challenges the area has historically faced related to poverty, unemployment, migration, and social inequality. The initiative was initiated by frontline professionals and community actors. These frontline actors realized that the vaccination plan as implemented on the regional level by national authorities did not match the needs of citizens in local neighbourhoods. Therefore, in parallel to the official policy, they initiated this small-scale vaccination strategy in local neighbourhoods, at weekly local markets. This strategy was specifically aimed at reaching vulnerable groups that (1) were the least likely group to get a vaccination themselves, and (2) were the group that would most benefit from getting vaccinated. The initiative started from a medical specialist and GP who coincidentally met during a television show of the local broadcaster and found out that they faced common challenges. They decided to work together and started providing accessible information at the local weekly market. By using her extensive social network, the community leader helped out in hiring a spot at the market. Soon, frontline professionals and community actors (Rustic Haven Helps Out) teamed-up to reach out to citizens and start the conversation. As they noticed that people often decided to get a vaccine after they received information and would want it right away, they actually started to provide vaccines on the local market. Following the initial success of the initiative (the initiators attracted attention and support from national media and local and national politicians), collaboration with other formal parties (like the national PHS) emerged, which then took over and incorporated this tailored vaccination strategy within their policy.

Case 10 (The Netherlands): Vaccination Campaign in Urk. This case report delves into a local, tailored vaccination strategy in the Municipality of Urk. This is an interesting case, because it serves valuable lessons in the importance of tailoring vaccination strategies to the unique characteristics and needs of local communities, even in the face of a global pandemic. This local crisis response in Urk can be seen as an illustration of robust governance. The robustness of this case not so much comes down to the ability to implement national policy measures and organize public health care (like vaccination provision), but all the more to the balancing act of protecting basic functions and goals (i.e. public order, stopping the spread of the virus) while also maintaining strong community values, leaving room for a diversity of perspectives, and keeping citizens 'on board'. The response was developed in a highly difficult context. After the start of the official vaccination campaign vaccination rates were relatively low in Urk, the village was characterised by strong hostility towards the national vaccination strategy mostly due to religious motivations and riots had emerged in the city in relation to the pandemic management. The national large-scale vaccination strategy that included large-scale vaccination locations where residents should go to (mostly outside Urk) did not work out as intended because, as interviewed public officials reported, of the social pressures that made that people did not dare to go get a vaccination. Antagonists of vaccinations even went demonstrating at vaccination locations and share 'information folders'. The local authorities in Urk therefore struggled with the translation of nationally announced measures to their local circumstances. General practitioners (GPs) initiated that they – as local, well-known and trusted professionals – would start vaccinating citizens within their practice. Initially the initiative struggled to start because of the lack of relations between the municipality, the national Public Health Service (PHS) and the GPs. There was very little interaction between national government level policy makers, and the local administration in Urk. The mayor used existing platforms, such as the safety region and direct interaction with the minister of Justice and Security, to probe attention for the specific situation in Urk and the specific case of religious communities. Deliberations were mostly ad-hoc and through informal venues like phone calls between the local government and the Minister of the Interior and Kingdom Relations and the Ministry of Justice and Security. Slowly communication was put in place among the different actors. In realizing this strategy, the local government was 'backstage', playing a supportive and communicative role. For GPs the precondition was that they only would administer the vaccines, and not be occupied with logistics and administrative tasks. The PHS coordinated this effort in such a way that all clinics had the amount of vaccines that was needed each day, and that they were restored in safe conditions.

Case 11 (The Netherlands): Plan Einstein. This case examines a local asylum reception strategy known as 'Plan Einstein' (formally: Utrecht Refugee Launch Pad - U-RLP) implemented during the 2015 refugee crisis in the historically diverse and disadvantaged Overvecht district in the city of Utrecht. Plan Einstein represented an innovative approach to asylum reception during the Refugee Crisis: in Overvecht, an office building located at the Einsteindreef was repurposed into an asylum shelter where 400 asylum seekers resided alongside 38 young residents from Utrecht. Notably, the educational and recreational offerings of Plan Einstein were accessible to asylum seekers, including those who have not yet obtained a residence permit, as well as to members of the local community (Dekker et al., 2021a). After the formation of a network with diverse partners in Utrecht, Plan Einstein was elaborated and the network of actors led by the city of Utrecht applied for EU fund for Urban Innovation Action, independently from and without oversight from the Ministry of Justice and Security (Geuijen et al., 2017, 2020). The horizontal dimension of multi-level governance becomes apparent in the collaboration between local public authorities and NGOs, as Plan Einstein was facilitated by the collaboration between these kinds of actors. Within the network, the municipality of Utrecht appeared to be leading, while the NGOs, such as Dutch Council for Refugees, contributed by (e.g.) sharing their knowledge and previous experiences regarding refugee reception. On the vertical dimension, the national organization COA was a stakeholder of plan Einstein but did not carry responsibility for the creation of Plan Einstein as a new approach. Although they were invited to the partnership, the COA decided against this. However, at the local level, the COA manager and professionals of the reception centre fully participated in Plan Einstein, including (partly) attending Plan Einstein consortium meetings

(Oliver et al., 2019). The response is therefore characterised by the emergence of a MLG venue that was bottom-up, formalised (developed in the framework of an EU-funded project) and multistakeholder (it was primarily a local alliance).

Case 12 (Spain): Vaccination in Aragón. This case focuses on the vaccination process in the Spanish region of Aragón, which can be considered a robust response to the covid-19 pandemic. In this region the vaccination process and prioritization were managed by a top-down non-binding advisory multidisciplinary crisis committee created by the Regional Government made up of the medical and nursing departments and other general departments, together with non-public stakeholders as technicians, veterinarians, pharmacists, logisticians, in total, some 12 or 14 people. The organization of the vaccination process was hierarchical, top-down, although senior civil servants interviewed stated that the opinions and suggestions coming, especially, from small local governments and neighbourhood associations were always taken into account. In rural areas with a very low population (in Aragón there are 731 municipalities, of which 670 have less than 1,000 inhabitants), the CCAA technicians met with local authorities, as needed, on a regular basis, and they were transferring the situation and the proposals when the measures were adapted in certain territories, creating WhatsApp groups, for agility, to share decisions and situations. Overall, this qualifies as an example of MLG arrangement, as different types of actors were separately consulted by the regional government, but not all actors gathered together in a venue.

8. Does MLG contribute to adaptation and innovation?

The analysis conducted in section 4 allows us to formulate several hypotheses about the contribution of MLG interactivity to the robust governance of crises.

Overall, and at the most basic level, the analysis conducted suggests that MLG seems to play an important role in favouring robust governance. Of the 12 robust cases analysed, 8 were characterised by some kind of MLG venues or arrangements, the remaining cases were characterised by highly visible horizontal relations (3 cases) and vertical relations (1 case). None of the robust cases analysed were characterised by centralised approaches with no interactivity. While the fact that we identified several cases where robust responses were produced in the absence of both horizontal and vertical relations might suggest that robust responses can be produced also without a fully structured MLG arrangement/venue. It might also be, however, that the involvement of specific actors on the vertical or horizontal dimension was not strictly needed due to the nature of the problem at stake in the five cases with no MLG. Interestingly, in one case characterised by horizontal relations but no vertical interactivity, involved actors complained about the impossibility to share their experiences with higher-level actors and explained that the absence of higher-level authorities in the MLG arrangement prevented any possibility that the innovative solutions identified locally could be replicated elsewhere in other localities. This suggests that while, on the one hand, the absence of interactivity along the vertical dimension of policymaking might not prevent the emergence of local robust responses, on the other hand, it might well reduce the likelihood that robust responses are generated locally and limit the scope for diffusion of innovative responses and practices within the multilevel governance system.

Another interesting insight emerged from the analysis concerns the role of practitioners in starting initiatives that led to MLG venues and robust responses. This was very evident in cases 9 and 10 in the Netherlands. While obviously this might be something specific about responses that take place and develop at the local level, this finding calls for a stronger focus in the role of practitioners and professionals in the governance of crises.

Table 8. Characteristics of the identified MLG venues (blue) and arrangements (grey)

	Primarily intergovernmental	Multi-stakeholders
Top-down	<p>Club</p> <p>Case 6 (blue), Case 12 (grey), Case 3 (blue)</p>	<p>Forum</p> <p>Case 1 (blue), Case 7 (blue), Case 4 (blue)</p>
Bottom-up	<p>Interest-group</p> <p>Case 10 (blue)</p>	<p>Assembly</p> <p>Case 11 (blue)</p>

Most of the responses analysed were characterised by the emergence of specific venues where actors involved in decision-making met and developed the responses. Table 8 provides an overview of the characteristics of the MLG venues/arrangements identified in the cases analysed.

The table suggests, first and foremost, that robust responses were produced by different types of MLG venues, including venues belonging to each of the four types identified in the first part of this report (club, forum, interest-group and assembly).

Second, the vast majority of the identified venues were top-down, i.e., created by and mostly steered/managed by governmental actors, typically from the highest level involved in the governance response. The only two venues that started or were steered bottom-up were those emerged in case 10 and case 11. In case 10, a key role was played by practitioners that collaborated then closely with governmental actors. In case 11, the Plan Einstein, the bottom-up initiative was developed in the framework of an EU project, which settled clear rules and objectives. This seems to suggest that an overarching coordination or steering of the venues/initiatives is a necessary precondition for MLG to contribute to the emergence of robust responses.

Third, table 8 suggests that – among the seven venues identified – the vast majority of them was characterised by non-hierarchical interactions among the actors involved. This suggests that prevalently hierarchical interactivity within MLG venues might obstruct the emergence of robust governance responses. While some top-down steering and coordination is needed, highly centralised leadership ensured by public authorities, our analysis suggests, might limit the contribution of other actors and therefore not lead to robust responses. Related to this point is the informal character of many of the venues that emerged from our analysis. Very few of the identified venues were institutionalised. Most of the venues were instead highly informal physical or non-physical venues. Overall, this suggests that collaborative informal relations are potential resources that can favour flexible adaptation and innovative thinking while at the same time reinforcing trust in the policy process and support for the institutions and organizations involved.

Fourth, our analysis seems to suggest that the composition of the MLG venues might not be crucial in determining the contribution of the venue to the robust governance of crisis situations. In fact, three of the identified venues were predominantly intergovernmental in nature, while four were mostly multistakeholder. A closer look at the three primarily intergovernmental venues

however suggests that, in all of these cases, no restriction was actually posed to the involvement of more non-public stakeholders, and that their limited number was largely related to the nature of the policy response at stake. Therefore, overall, the analysis suggests that a flexible open membership of MLG venues and a tendency to include all of the relevant stakeholder can contribute to produce more robust governance responses. The presence of a limited number of stakeholders constraints the range of policy options to the routine modes of intervention preferred by public authorities, constraining the flexibility and adaptive mindset that is requested to public policymakers in times of crises and eventually preventing the emergence of innovative solutions (e.g., solution proposed by actors excluded from the policymaking venue). At the same time, a close or restricted membership of MLG venues might also reduce the legitimacy of the responses produced.

Overall, by combing the insights illustrated so far, the analysis conducted seems to suggest that, while different types of MLG venues can all produce robust governance responses, an “informal forum” might represent the ideal type of venue in terms of its contribution to robustness. Such variant of MLG combines the inclusion of an ample range of stakeholders, enhancing political legitimacy and openness towards innovative standpoints, with top-down initiative and steering. Such combination of factors, our analysis suggests, can favour efficient decision-making. Top-down steering, in particular, has the potential to limit problems related to the participation of very high numbers of actors, which can otherwise also be coupled with volatility in terms of commitment and engagement in the policymaking venue and decisions aimed at generating consensus among all the involved actors rather than at effectively solving problems. Informal rather than highly formalised fora, in particular, in which public and non-public actors convened engage not only in formal decision-making but also in more horizontal activities of exchange of experiences and information, seems to set the basis for adaptability and innovation, favoured by informality and peer-to-peer trust relations.

Finally, it can be noticed that the vast majority of the venues identified in the previous section were created *ad hoc* to formulate responses to the crisis. Only in two cases preexisting venues were used. Furthermore, many of the identified venues in many respects challenged or went beyond formal existing distribution of competences in the policy field. Once again, this suggests that flexible and ad hoc solutions might be more useful to contribute to robust governance.

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